

EU-HIP – REPORT

EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform

This activity is supported by co-funding from the European Union's EU4Health programme under Grant Agreement Nr 101102774 EU-HIP. Views and opinions expressed do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable number: D4.1 Landscape analysis

Due date: 31.03.2024

Dissemination Level¹: PUBLIC

Work Package: WP4

Lead Beneficiary: THL, Sciensano

Contributing Beneficiaries: MIN-SAL, SPMS, NIPH, SSI, RIVM, NIJZ; all

This activity is supported by co-funding from the European Union's EU4Health programme under Grant Agreement Nr 101102774 EU-HIP. Views and opinions expressed do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HaDEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Restraint UE = Classified with the classification level "Restraint UE" according to Commission Decision 2001/844 and amendments

Confidential UE = Classified with the mention of the classification level "Confidential UE" according to Commission Decision 2001/844 and amendments

Secret UE = Classified with the mention of the classification level "Secret UE" according to Commission Decision 2001/844 and amendments

WP4 – Sustainability

D4.1 – Landscape Analysis Report

Status	FINAL report
Due date of the milestone	31-03-2024
Work Package	WP4
Lead partners for this deliverable	THL, Sciensano
Main Authors (in alphabetical order)	Shona Cosgrove, Persephone Doupi, Joris van Loenhout, Laura Laurenzi, Léonore Nasiadka, Vanessa Mendes, Valeria Proietti, Miriam Saso, Federica Sperti, Miia Ryhänen-Tompuri, Lucrezia Valieri
Contributors (in alphabetical order)	Emanuel Brađašević, Kristine Brodahl Rossa O'Donnell, Paulius Gradeckas, Guđrún Audur Haraldsdóttir, Ionel Iosif, Alexandru Iuhas, Pikka Jokelainen, Larisa Moga, Kim Ng, Charlotte Larsson Sandén, Dalibor Stanimirovic, Lucija Tepej-Jocic, Lavinia Rusu, Susan van den Hof, Jos van Vlerken
Editors:	Persephone Doupi, Marja Suomela, Tricia Larose, Miia Ryhänen-Tompuri, Pikka Jokelainen

EU-HIP Consortium Partners	Organisation category	Countries
STATENS SERUM INSTITUT (SSI)	National Public Health Institute	Denmark
SCIENSANO	National Institute of Public Health	Belgium
HRVATSKI ZAVOD ZA JAVNO ZDRAVSTVO (CIPH)	National Institute of Public Health	Croatia
MINISTARSTVO ZDRAVSTVA REPUBLIKE HRVATSKE (MOH-HR)	Ministry of Health	Croatia
BUNDESMINISTERIUM FUER GESUNDHEIT (BMG)	Federal Ministry of Health	Germany
EMBAETTI LANDLAEKNIS (LANDL)	Directorate of Health	Iceland
MINISTERO DELLA SALUTE (MINSAL)	Ministry of Health	Italy
SVEIKATOS APSAUGOS MINISTERIJOS EKSTREMALIU SVEIKATAI SITUACIJU CENTRAS (HESC)	Health Emergency Situation Center, Ministry of Health Protection	Lithuania
RIJKSINSTITUUT VOOR VOLKSGEZONDHEID EN MILIEU (RIVM)	National Institute of Public Health and the Environment	Netherlands
FOLKEHELSEINSTITUTTET (NIPH)	National Institute of Public Health	Norway
HELSEDIREKTORATET (HDIR)	Directorate of Health	Norway
SERVICOS PARTILHADOS DO MINISTERIO DA SAUDE EPE (SPMS)	Shared Services of the Ministry of Health	Portugal
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE SAUDE DR. RICARDO JORGE (INSA)	The National Health Institute	Portugal
ADMINISTRACAO CENTRAL DO SISTEMA DESAUDE IP (ACSS)	The Central Administration of the Health System	Portugal
MINISTERIO DA SAUDE - REPUBLICA PORTUGUESA (MS-DGS)	Ministry of Health	Portugal
INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE SANATATE PUBLICA (INSP)	National Institute of Public Health	Romania
SERVICIUL DE TELECOMUNICATII SPECIALE (STS)	Special Telecommunications Service	Romania
NACIONALNI INSTITUT ZA JAVNO ZDRAVJE (NIJZ)	National Institute of Public Health	Slovenia
FOLKHALSOMYNDIGHETEN (FOHM)	National Public Health Agency	Sweden
TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS (THL)	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare	Finland
MINISTERE SANTE DE LA SANTE ET DE LA PREVENTION (MoH FR)	Ministry of Health	France

EU-HIP – REPORT	1
EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform	1
Executive Summary	6
1. Introduction	9
2. Methodology.....	11
3. Landscape analysis findings	15
3.1 Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)	15
3.1.1 Digital infrastructures and systems.....	15
3.1.2 Legislative aspects	20
3.1.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network.....	20
3.2 Pathogens of high pandemic potential (PHPP).....	22
3.2.1 Digital infrastructures and systems.....	22
3.2.2 Legislative aspects	32
3.2.3 Key actors and stakeholder's network.....	33
3.3 Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear threats (CBRN)	34
3.3.1 Digital infrastructures and systems.....	34
3.3.2 Legislative aspects	35
3.3.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network.....	35
3.4 Medical Countermeasures (MCM).....	37
3.4.1 Digital infrastructures and systems.....	37
3.4.2 Legislative aspects	45
3.4.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network.....	47
4 Preparing the ground for EU-HIP sustainability.....	48
5 References.....	49
6 Annexes	50
Annex 1: EU-HIP Landscape mapping tool	50
Annex 2: AMR supplementary materials	51
Annex 3: PHPP supplementary materials	55
Annex 4. CBRN supplementary materials	69
Annex 5. MCM supplementary materials.....	74

List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMR	Antimicrobial resistance
ATHINA	Advanced Technology for Health INtelligence and Action
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological or Nuclear (threats)
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
D	Deliverable
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EU-HIP	EU interoperability with HERA's IT platform
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HERA	European Health Emergency preparedness and Response Authority
HIS	Health Information System (national)
IHR	International Health Regulations
IT	Information Technology
M	Month
MCM	Medical Countermeasures
MERS	Middle East respiratory syndrome
MS	Milestone
PHIRI	Population Health Information Research Infrastructure
PHPP	Pathogens with High Pandemic Potential
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
SARS	severe acute respiratory syndrome
T	Task
TEHDAS JA	Towards the European Health Data Space Joint Action
UPIN	Unique personal identifier
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

HERA is currently developing the Advanced Technology for Health Intelligence and Action (ATHINA) IT system. Strong collaboration with Member States is a critical component of HERA's ATHINA IT system that will integrate Member State information and data sharing related to stockpiling of medical countermeasures (e.g. medicines, vaccines and PPE), supply-chain management, and aggregated health data.

ATHINA will only be operational if Member States have strong national IT systems that are interoperable with HERA's IT platform and other relevant systems. This is a challenge that needs to be addressed at country-level, and in collaboration with countries across the EU/EEA. Aligned with this challenge, the EU-HIP project (EU interoperability with HERA's IT Platform) supports participating countries to develop, implement, enhance and improve national IT systems in an efficient and coordinated manner towards needed interoperability with ATHINA IT. In this manner, EU-HIP facilitates a robust and effective EU response to cross-border health emergencies.

In the EU-HIP project, sustainability hinges on a thorough mapping and analysis of national IT systems in alignment with HERA's priorities. This approach guides the first step of the overall, multifaceted sustainability work of the project.

A baseline activity of the EU-HIP project, and the focus of this report, is the current landscape analysis of participating countries' IT systems (WP4, Task 4.1) covering the mapping and analysis of digital infrastructures and systems (including data and their standards), key actors/stakeholder networks and their roles, as well as pertinent legislative frameworks.

Details on HERA's ATHINA IT specifications and operating procedures are of central importance to the focus of this work. Hence, WP4 partners, in collaboration with WP1 and WP5 ensure the alignment of EU-HIP activities with those of HERA and the ATHINA IT development team.

For the gathering of the information presented in this report, a two-step methodology has been implemented. Using the input from previous projects and international initiatives, a data-gathering tool (Annex 1) in the form of a questionnaire was developed by the EU-HIP partners in close collaboration with HERA. The final version of the questionnaire encompasses three priority cross-border health threats identified by HERA:

- Antimicrobial resistance (AMR),
- Pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP) and
- Chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear (CBRN) threats.

For each health threat, the tool was used to gather data on the digital infrastructures, specialized IT systems, key stakeholders and the regulatory framework governing the use of associated data. Additionally, a distinct section focusing on medical countermeasures (MCMs) was developed to compile information on the availability and accessibility of countries' digital readiness concerning various types of MCM, including medicines, medical equipment and personal protective equipment. The information gathered underwent a thorough review and validity checking process, involving representatives from each EU-HIP partner. Furthermore, an external reviewer, not directly involved in the writing of the report, examined its content to further enhance its quality. Subsequently, the data were aggregated on consortium level for the public report, while country-specific details provided in the data-gathering tool and generated by the analysis of the collected material were retained for further use in EU-HIP work.

In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with country-specific experts in the context of the agreed country visits, delving deeper into each topic from the landscape

analysis. The goal was to gain insights into the functionality of the identified systems, the roles and interactions of key stakeholders and additional details about pertinent legislations. Country-specific materials will also be used to support further work within the EU-HIP project, such as the identification of key areas of improvement and the actions needed to achieve interoperability with the upcoming HERA's IT platform, ATHINA.

The first country visit took place in Croatia in November 2023. The provisional timeline for the upcoming country visits is Lithuania in April 2024, Denmark in May 2024 and Iceland in May or June 2024. Key findings of country visits will be reported in the level of detail agreed with the respective countries as part of MS11 (due M24).

The work presented in D4.1 was carried out in collaboration with the EU-HIP WP1 and WP5 teams. Starting in mid-January 2024, all the information gathered was analyzed and – following several iterations with consortium partners – summarized in the current report. The findings from the landscape analysis will be used as the starting point for WP5's task T5.2 (Implementation of improvements) and act as the guideline of the country-based IT systems improvement, and the basis for the interoperability technical specifications with HERA platform (T5.3).

In the area of AMR, our findings show that digitized systems of varying profiles are in place in the majority of EU-HIP consortium partners' countries and are utilized for data sharing with established international systems, as well as reporting nationally and internationally.

Utilization of AI and secure cloud solutions is still at an early stage, with only three countries being at the planning phase at the time of the project data collection. Gathering of AMR data relies on international documentation standards in the majority of countries.

Threat detection is still primarily event-based, with indicator based in the second place. Detection and assessment of threats is still an activity heavily relying on use of experts, although there are some first trends towards automatization.

EU-HIP work on PHPP was based on a list of pathogens which was compiled by drawing upon those referenced in the most recent update provided by the WHO² along with key documents associated with the activities of HERA³.

All countries reported that operational IT / digitized systems are in place for PHPP and related diseases, at least for COVID-19 and Influenza, but often combined with other pathogens. Nine out of fifteen countries indicated that an IT system is in place for all PHPP. Ten countries reported using standardized forms and templates for data capture and/or reporting for the whole list of selected PHPP; still most often data capture is made through a template form sent by physicians of laboratories personnel to Public Health authorities. Overall, the most frequently reported data sources for the selected PHPP are hospital data, primary care and infectious disease registry data.

Threat detection plays a crucial role in effective surveillance of PHPP by enabling early identification and data-driven decision-making to mitigate the impact of emerging infectious diseases. Countries employ diverse methodologies and tools to detect threats, depending on the resources and technologies available (Table 19). The proportion of expert involvement varies from pathogen to pathogen. Nevertheless, only a few countries, and for specific pathogens, have an automatic or partially automatic system in place for the detection of threats. Similarly, validation and assessment of threats are also heavily expert-dependent rather than automated activities.

Most of EU-HIP consortium countries also reported **monitoring CBRN threats**, similarly as other health threats. Work related to detection, mitigation and management of CBRN threats involves a wide range of activities, with data and information gathered from several sources and a broad range of stakeholders. Nine out of the fifteen EU-HIP countries reported that an

²<https://www.who.int/activities/prioritizing-diseases-for-research-and-development-in-emergency-contexts>

³ https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/hera_work-plan_2022_en_0.pdf

operational IT/ digitized system is in place for one or more of the domains – chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear. Functionalities to present and export data are relatively limited and AI solutions are not employed in national systems or considered at the moment, with the exception of one country.

The area of MCM was addressed by an accordingly tailored section of the EU-HIP questionnaire. Although the general structure applied in other topic areas was maintained in terms of key domains of interest (i.e., digital infrastructure, key stakeholders and legal framework) the MCM part of the questionnaire included also topic-specific themes such as stockpiling.

According to the responses received, almost half of EU-HIP-consortium countries report the presence of a digitized system for MCM. The mentioned systems may be in various stages of development and maturity, as well as coverage of the MCM domain. Medicinal products and medical devices appear to be the most addressed MCM categories, with PPE following rather closely.

The category of MCM mostly reported in stockpile were PPE – perhaps a reflection of COVID-19 pandemic proximity – with medicines and medical devices following up. Monitoring practices applied to the stockpiling chain concern primarily medicinal products, with seven of the consortium partner countries indicating the presence of monitoring practices. Automation of problem detection appears to still be in an early phase, with only five out of the seven responding positively to the question of automated solutions use for supply-chain problems identification. Furthermore, amongst the queried countries, six indicated the use of AI-driven solutions or similar to manage stockpile quantities.

When reviewing the results of the EU-HIP Landscape analysis, it is important to keep in mind certain **limitations** identified in the data collection process, which may limit the overall validity and accuracy of the findings. These include aspects related to questionnaire completion rates, content sensitivity, and availability of experts to respond in relation to the wide scope of the work – a very broad, multi-actor and dynamic field of activity. Moreover, changes may have occurred after the completion and closing of the data collection updates in mid-February 2024.

The findings of the landscape analysis presented in the D4.1 report will provide EU-HIP with the reference points for **building towards sustainability**. EU-HIP will benefit from reviewing main findings and lessons learned from prior relevant projects, by utilizing them as a means of focusing on identified areas of both best practices and clear development gaps.

Taking into account the EU-HIP project's main objective of interoperability support and facilitation, in the forthcoming work the consortium will be promoting **synergies** between the EHDS activities for protection against serious cross-border threats to health, and public health surveillance or activities ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare and EU-HIP activities; and conversely, aim to outline how EU-HIP sustainability outcomes could be useful for the EHDS ecosystem.

1. Introduction

The Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) was established as a new European Commission Directorate-General on 16 September 2021. As a pillar of the European Health Union, HERA's mission is to prevent, detect, and rapidly respond to health emergencies⁴.

HERA anticipates threats and potential cross-border health crises by leveraging public health surveillance and public health intelligence for horizon scanning and signal detection to improve situational awareness for evidence-based decision making. HERA builds and expands upon necessary capacities to ensure a well-coordinated European response when a public health emergency is declared.

HERA is currently developing the Advanced Technology for Health Intelligence and Action (ATHINA) IT system⁵. Strong collaboration with Member States is a critical component of HERA's ATHINA IT system that will integrate Member State information and data sharing related to stockpiling of medical countermeasures (e.g. masks and vaccines), supply-chain management, and aggregated health data. HERA's intelligence gathering will support four pre-established priority areas:

1. Pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP),
2. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR),
3. Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear threats (CBRN), and
4. Medical countermeasures (MCM), such as medicinal products, medical devices and personal protective equipment (PPE).

ATHINA will only be operational if Member States have strong national IT systems that are interoperable with the platform and other relevant systems. This is a challenge that needs to be addressed at country-level, and in collaboration with countries across the EU/EEA. Aligned with this challenge, the EU-HIP project (EU interoperability with HERA's IT Platform) supports participating countries to develop, implement, enhance and improve national IT systems in an efficient and coordinated manner towards needed interoperability with ATHINA. In this manner, EU-HIP facilitates a robust and effective EU response to cross-border health emergencies.

In the EU-HIP project, sustainability hinges on a thorough mapping and analysis of national IT systems in alignment with HERA's priorities. This approach guides the first step of the overall, multifaceted sustainability work of the project.

A baseline activity of the EU-HIP project, and the focus of this report, is to conduct a landscape analysis of participating countries' IT systems (Task 4.1) covering the mapping and analysis of digital infrastructures and systems (including data and their standards), key actors/stakeholder networks and their roles, as well as pertinent legislative frameworks. Details on HERA's ATHINA IT specifications and operating procedures are of central importance to the focus of this work. Hence WP4 partners, in collaboration with WP1 and WP5 ensure the alignment of EU-HIP activities with those of HERA and the ATHINA IT development team.

EU-HIP, in collaboration with HERA, contributes to the achievement of the EU4Health Programme⁶ general objective of protecting people in the Union from serious cross-border

⁴ Health Emergency Preparedness and Response (HERA)

⁵ HERA IT System 'ATHINA' to collect intelligence and assess threats: call for tender published - HERA - April 2023

⁶ https://health.ec.europa.eu/funding/eu4health-programme-2021-2027-vision-healthier-european-union_en

threats to health and strengthening the responsiveness of health systems and coordination among the Member States.

2 Methodology

For the gathering of the information presented in this report, a two-step methodology has been implemented consisting of 1) a landscape analysis (providing the bulk of background material for this report) and 2) a series of country visits complementing the results of the landscape analysis (country visits are still in progress at the time of authoring this report and will be completed before the end of 2024).

1. Landscape analysis

During the preparatory phase of the project proposal, the consortium partners started to identify potential projects whose findings could offer valuable insights for T4.1. The aim was to leverage the methodologies and outcomes of country mappings from previous initiatives such as the TEHDAS JA⁷ and the PHIRI project⁸. However, it was recognized that the assessment tool used in these projects would require adaptation to address the specific topics of HERA's priority areas covered within the EU-HIP project. Therefore, additional input on health preparedness and response aspects was sought from the methodology implemented in the Joint External Evaluations performed by the World Health Organization (WHO)⁹.

Using the input from previous projects and international initiatives, a data-gathering tool (Annex 1) in the form of a questionnaire was developed by the EU-HIP partners in close collaboration with HERA. To ensure alignment with ATHINA's platform specifications and operational procedures, extensive consultations were conducted from January to October 2023. These consultations involved HERA and representatives from Member States and focused on providing feedback to refine the questionnaire components. An interim report outlining the initial development of the tool was presented in May 2023 (Milestone 8 – Data collection methodology for landscape mapping) for the consortium's use.

The final version of the questionnaire encompasses three priority cross-border health threats identified by HERA:

- Antimicrobial resistance (AMR),
- Pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP) and
- Chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear (CBRN) threats.

Regarding the PHPP, in agreement with HERA, data were collected on COVID-19, Influenza viruses, Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever and Dengue.

For each health threat, the tool gathers data on the areas of digital infrastructures, specialized IT systems, key stakeholders and the regulatory framework governing the use of associated data. Table 1 provides an overview of the core areas and subdomains covered in the tool for AMR, PHPP and CBRN.

⁷ Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space – TEHDAS

⁸ Population Health Information Research Infrastructure - PHIRI

⁹ Joint External Evaluation (JEE) - International Health Regulation M&E Framework - WHO

Table 1: Overview of the core domains and subdomains covered by the EU-HIP data gathering tool

Core domains	Subdomains
Digital infrastructures and systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sources • Data linkage and sharing • Data storage • Standards and quality • Threat indicators
Key actors and stakeholders' networks	
Legislative aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislation • Strategy

Additionally, a distinct section focusing on medical countermeasures (MCMs) (Table 2) was developed to compile information on the availability and accessibility of countries' digital readiness concerning various types of MCM, including medicines, medical equipment and personal protective equipment.

Table 2: Overview of the core domains and subdomains covered in the tool for MCM

Core domains	Subdomains	Topics
Digital infrastructures and systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sources • Stockpiling • Supply chain • Artificial intelligence tools • Data sharing • Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicines • Medical devices • Personal protection equipment
Key actors and stakeholders' networks		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicines • Medical devices • Personal protection equipment
Legislative aspects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legislation • Strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicines • Medical devices • Personal protection equipment

In early October 2023, the questionnaire was distributed to all Consortium Members with a completion deadline set for the end of December 2023. The EU-HIP partners were tasked with identifying in their countries experts on the different topics of interest and sharing with them the tool so that they could provide the necessary information. The work was carried out in collaboration with the EU-HIP WP1 and WP5. Starting in January 2024, all the information gathered was analyzed and – following several iterations with consortium partners – summarized in the current report. The findings from the landscape analysis will be used as the starting point for the T5.2 and act as the guideline of the country-based IT systems improvement, and the basis for the interoperability technical specifications with HERA platform (T5.3).

The information gathered underwent a thorough review and accuracy checking process, involving representatives from each EU-HIP partner. Furthermore, one of the consortium's experts not directly involved in the writing of the report, reviewed its content throughout to further enhance its quality. Subsequently, the data was aggregated. Country-specific reports will be generated by the EU-HIP consortium for a subset of countries, as detailed in the second section of the methodology.

2. Country visits

In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were conducted with country-specific experts, delving deeper into each topic from the landscape analysis. The goal was to gain insights into the functionality of the identified systems, the roles and interactions of key stakeholders and additional details about pertinent legal aspects. The interviews build upon the tool's pre-existing questions, encouraging experts to provide additional information beyond what has been already shared during the first phase. The analysis of the materials collected during the country visit is shared with the country of interest for review, and after approval, with HERA. The country is also encouraged to publicly share the report to benefit the larger community. Country-specific materials will also be used to support further work within the EU-HIP project, such as the identification of key areas of improvement in WP5 and the actions needed to achieve interoperability with the upcoming HERA's IT platform, ATHINA.

Part of this work has already been integrated into the current version of the D4.1 Landscape Analysis Report. The first country visit took place in Croatia in November 2023. The provisional timeline for the upcoming country visits is Lithuania in April 2024, Denmark in May 2024 and Iceland in May or June 2024.

3. Limitations of the Landscape analysis work

When reviewing the results of the EU-HIP Landscape analysis, it is important to keep in mind certain limitations identified in our data collection process, which may limit the validity and accuracy of our findings. These include aspects related to questionnaire completion rates, content sensitivity, and availability of experts to respond in relation to the wide scope of the work.

1. Questionnaire completion rates

In order to estimate the representativeness and coverage achieved in the EU-HIP questionnaire data collection process, we have calculated the degree of response completeness for each country of the 15 EU-HIP Consortium members for the three questionnaire domains covered in each studied topic: Digital infrastructures and systems, Key actors and stakeholders' network and Legislative aspects.

In Annexes 2-5, presenting supplementary materials for each topic, we provide at an aggregate level the degree of completion of the respective questionnaire module (AMR, PHPP, CBRN, MCM).

Readers should keep in mind that the respective calculations were performed in February 2024, after which some further modifications and updates may have taken place with regard to content of original responses, which have not been accounted for. Nevertheless, the updates most likely would have a positive, rather than a negative impact.

2. Content sensitivity concerning certain areas of focus

Particularly the thematic areas of CBRN, MCM and related preparedness belong to the realm of sensitive national information. As a result, several of our consortium participants explicitly declined to provide information to the respective modules, based on these

grounds. The approach cannot be but respected and was also identified at the application preparation stage as a possible limitation in EU-HIP activities. No Member State is obliged to supply information the disclosure of which it considers contrary to the essential interests of its security.

3. Consortium expertise

The scope of the work was wide, and availability of specific expertise to respond or review responses at country-level may have varied. Matters related to CBRN and MCM are often under the responsibility of several national agencies depending on the domain and the National Medicines Agency, respectively. Those organizations, in turn, do not feature for the most part among EU-HIP consortium participants, since EU-HIP has a stronger emphasis in the area of public health. This possible limitation was also recognized already at the time of project application preparation, and it is being addressed through liaising with the appropriate stakeholders nationally, as well as identifying EU-funded projects, with which it is important to seek synergies. Identifying examples of pertinent projects, reviewing their work and results, as well as actively establishing contacts, will lead to stronger collaboration under the umbrella of the EU-HIP sustainability work.

DISCLAIMER: Please keep in mind the aforementioned limitations when assessing the validity and generalizability of the findings presented in D4.1. EU-HIP is aiming to cover a very broad, multi-actor and dynamic field of activity, and changes may have occurred after the completion and closing of our data collection updates (mid-February 2024).

3 Landscape analysis findings

3.1 Antimicrobial Resistance (AMR)

3.1.1 Digital infrastructures and systems

3.1.1.1 Data sources

Standardised approach to AMR intelligence gathering

Regarding the usage of standardized approaches for public health intelligence gathering, several relevant pieces of information emerged from most of the countries analysed.

Standardised approaches are applied by seven countries regarding AMR intelligence gathering. Five countries use multiple gathering systems or different specific structures for data collection, depending on the type of pathogen. Specifically, multiple surveillance systems are monitored and fed in parallel, namely those at regional, national and European levels (sometimes involving cooperation with experts within European networks). Furthermore, depending on the type of pathogen, different national bodies and institutes come into play (e.g. bloodstream infections, clostridioides, healthcare associated infections in intensive care). Often laboratory data are obtained from communications from general practitioners, nursing homes and hospitals. In some cases, data on HRMO (Highly Resistant Micro-Organisms) come from laboratories, data on antibiotic consumption from general practitioners. Moreover, some countries have a health system divided into regions and municipalities that is responsible for implementing health data allowing the different actors involved to interact. For two countries the collection and notification on AMR is partial: in one of the countries analysed the CPO (Carbapenemase-Producing Organisms) and MRSA (Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus) are notifiable according to a lab-based system.

Table 3: Standardised approach for intelligence gathering related to AMR

	Number of countries reported
Unique gathering system for all the AMR-related data	7/15 countries
Multiple gathering systems or different structures for collection	5/15 countries
Partial data notification and collection	2/15 countries

Data sources used for intelligence gathering

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of the most used data sources for AMR intelligence gathering.

Figure 1: Data sources used for intelligence gathering related to AMR

Level of data collection

All countries analysed indicated that AMR data is collected and monitored on the national level. Furthermore, several countries collect and monitor AMR data also at the regional (seven countries), as well as at local level (five countries).

Operational IT/digitized systems

In almost all the countries analysed (11/15) IT/digitized systems are in place. These IT/digitized systems were described as operational for one or more of the pathogen monitoring domains: signal acquisition, data analysis or reporting.

Table 4: Operational IT/digitized systems for AMR among EU-HIP consortium countries.

	Number of countries reported
Signal capture	7/15 countries
Data analysis	8/15 countries
Reporting purposes	9/15 countries

Nine countries mentioned that their operational IT/digitized systems offer functionalities to present and export data. Among them, the most cited ones are the availability of dashboards for AMR data visualisation (by four countries), regular reports (by four countries) and use of BI tools as SAP Business Object or Power BI (by three countries).

Use of Artificial Intelligence in surveillance

None of the countries analysed employs AI solutions in the systems currently in use. Three countries are planning the application of such solutions as part of their upcoming internal regulations on collection and management of health data.

3.1.1.2 Data storage

IT infrastructures for the storage and processing of health data are in place at national level for almost all the countries surveyed (14/15). Some countries implement repository processes even at regional level (5/15). However, a secure cloud for AMR data is absent for almost all of the countries analysed, with the exception of two.

3.1.1.3 Standards and data quality

Use of standards

Use of a standardized electronic format and transfer of data to a centralized database are applied to a large extent, in 14 out of the 15 countries. On the other hand, a metadata catalogue for the information sources used in AMR surveillance is available in only half of the countries analysed.

Standardized terminologies in support of AMR health data surveillance are reported by almost all the countries analysed, even if there does not appear to be a prevailing terminology.

Table 5: Standardised terminologies used in AMR among EU-HIP countries

	ICD-10 ⁽¹⁾	LOINC ⁽²⁾	ATC ⁽³⁾	SNOMED-CT ⁽⁴⁾
Number of countries reported	9	4	9	6

⁽¹⁾ ICD-10 is the 10th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Disease and Related Health Problems (ICD), a WHO medical classification list for clinical terms and diagnoses to record statistics on diseases (signs and symptoms, abnormal findings, complaints, social circumstances, and external causes of injury) in primary, secondary and tertiary care, as well as on cause of death certificates.

⁽²⁾ Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC) is a common language (set of identifiers, names, and codes) for identifying Laboratory and Clinical tests, measurements and observations.

⁽³⁾ The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) classification system provides a differentiation of the active substances into different groups according to the organ or system on which they act and their therapeutic, pharmacological and chemical properties. Drugs are classified in groups at five different levels. The level 1 includes 14 main anatomical and pharmacological groups; the level 2 refers to a pharmacological and therapeutic subgroup; the level 3 and 4 comprehend chemical, pharmacological and therapeutic subgroup; the level 5 put together chemical substances.

⁽⁴⁾ The Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED-CT) is a comprehensive clinical health terminology, encoding the meanings of terms often used in healthcare settings, such as symptoms, signs, diagnoses, procedures, clinical findings, and body structures. Its database is also able to distinguish between aetiologies, pharmaceuticals, specimens, and medical devices.

Regularity of input and response

Concerning regularity of data inputs, for most of the countries analysed AMR data is provided on an annual basis. The countries reported different frequencies of regularity depending on the purpose and the type of pathogens. Specifically, exceptions to the surveillance times occur for the following pathogens: MRSA e CPO on the basis of findings in one country; AST (weekly) and HRMO (bi-weekly) in one country; ABR under daily input in one country.

Two of the analysed countries respectively activate regular surveillance just for notifiable resistant bacteria and switch on ad hoc monitoring in case of alert.

Table 6: Regularity of data inputs for AMR

	Number of countries reported
Yearly	9/15 countries
Monthly/Weekly	3/15 countries
Daily/Routinely/Continuous	7/15 countries
Ad Hoc/Real-time	4/15 countries

3.1.1.4 Threat indicators

Potential health threats are detected above all through the recording and analysis of individual events and through the monitoring of indicators recorded by the detection systems implemented.

Table 7: Threat detection modalities

	Event-based ⁽¹⁾	Indicator-based ⁽²⁾	Syndromic surveillance ⁽³⁾	Threshold ⁽⁴⁾
Number of countries reported	11	9	5	2

⁽¹⁾ Event-based detection is the organised and rapid capture of information about events that are a potential risk to public health, referring to a method of monitoring and tracking the occurrence of specific health-related events in a population. Health authorities and medical practitioners actively collect and analyse data on specific events, such as cases of illness, hospital admissions or deaths.

⁽²⁾ Indicator-based is the systematic (regular) collection, monitoring and analysis and interpretation of structured data, to track specific health-related indicators such as incidence or prevalence rates in a population. Health authorities collect and analyse data on specific indicators such as the number of cases of a specific disease, the incidence of hospital admissions or the prevalence of a risk factor.

⁽³⁾ Syndromic surveillance entails tracking patterns of symptoms or syndromes (clusters of symptoms) in the population. This can provide early indications of unusual health events before a specific diagnosis is confirmed.

⁽⁴⁾ The threshold method involves establishing predefined criteria or thresholds that trigger a response when surpassed. These criteria could be based on specific epidemiological indicators, such as the number of cases, transmission rate, or severity of illness. Once the predetermined threshold is met or exceeded, appropriate actions are initiated to address the identified threat.

Trend surveillance has been also notified by three countries. The monitoring of AMR detects and tracks trends in microbial populations including drug-resistant microorganisms and resistant determinants (genes or resistances mechanisms/patterns).

The detection phase and the assessment of collected surveillance data are performed always through the involvement of experts for the analysis and effective determination of the emergency level of the information. In a few exceptional cases among the countries analysed, the two levels of surveillance include two verification phases: a first automated phase and a second phase which relies on the involvement of experts.

3.1.1.5 Data linkage and sharing

Data linkage

As regards the method of aggregation and identification of data, the analysis revealed a dichotomy between countries which use a single identifier and those that use multiple identifiers. Specifically, seven countries use a single ID number at national level and three countries use multiple identifiers depending on the context and the type of data associated to the person.

Data sharing

The collected and monitored data is shared with European and international organizations, as well as with other EU Member States. The systems most involved in AMR data exchange are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: EU and international surveillance systems used for sharing AMR data

Figure 2: EU and international surveillance systems used for sharing AMR data

Other European and international organisations were also mentioned, but less frequently, including the Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources Initiatives (EIOS) or the European Surveillance of Antimicrobial Consumption Network (ESAC-Net).

3.1.2 Legislative aspects

In almost all the countries surveyed (12/15), internal exchange of health data among the various national stakeholders was reported, while for half of these countries this exchange was highlighted as being regulated by legislation.

Table 8: Internal exchange of health data on AMR

	Legal framework provided	Sharing with internal stakeholders
Number of countries reported	10	12

Agreements for sharing data

Twelve out of 15 countries reported implementing data sharing towards other countries and international organisations. Most commonly data are exchanged with ECDC, EWRS, WHO, EARS-Net, with the distribution shown in Table 9.

Table 9: International/EU institutions engaged for the AMR data sharing

	ECDC	WHO	EWRS
Number of countries reported	5	3	3

With regards to the provision of a preparedness plan for AMR, eight countries declared having one, most of them having been developed at national level and in coordination with other plans.

3.1.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network

The various stakeholders concerning AMR and their respective roles in different consortium member countries include the following institutions and organizations:

- **Ministries of Health** provide political oversight, finance and interministerial coordination, including national plans to combat antibiotic resistance.
- **National public health institutions** are responsible for health preparedness planning, guidelines, notification, regulations, coordination of response across health sector and agencies; surveillance; national alerts; collection of information, quality control of data sent by laboratories, and analysis and dissemination of data.
- **Public organizations specific to antimicrobial resistance** exist in some countries with responsibility for analysis of alert reports and provision of expert advice,

contributing to the development and application of the national and regional strategy for the prevention of infections associated with care and the control of AMR.

- **Medicine agencies** are responsible for regulation, safety protocols, supply, and accessibility.
- **Food safety and veterinary agencies** are responsible for i.a. regulation and oversight, surveillance and monitoring.
- **Regional authorities** that are in charge of hospital management; primary care services and municipal preparedness planning.
- **Hospitals and local service providers** responsible for regional management of the national health system; risk assessment and risk management; local institutional infection prevention and control.
- **Laboratories** yielding and conducting extraction of antibiotic resistance data; diagnosing and reporting.
- **Other public institutions** such as patient safety and social insurance institutions.

A more detailed overview of main AMR stakeholders and networks examples in some of the EU-HIP consortium countries is available in Annex 2, Table 1.

3.2 Pathogens of high pandemic potential (PHPP)

Declared as one of the top three health threats requiring EU coordination, pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPPs) are those that possess characteristics making them capable of causing widespread and severe outbreaks across different regions. The identification and monitoring of PHPPs are crucial for preparedness and rapid response to emerging infectious diseases. In 2016, the World Health Organization (WHO), in collaboration with experts in the field, assessed and published a list of PHPPs based on transmission, severity and evolutionary potential characteristics. After the declaration of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, the list was updated¹⁰.

In preparation of the EU-HIP questionnaire, a list of pathogens was compiled, drawing upon those referenced in the most recent update provided by the WHO, along with two documents associated with the activities of HERA^{11,12}. The list contains (in alphabetical order):

- Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19);
- Chikungunya disease;
- Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever (CCHF);
- Dengue fever;
- Ebola and Marburg diseases;
- Influenza virus disease;
- Lassa fever;
- Rift Valley fever;
- Severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and Middle East respiratory syndrome coronavirus (MERS) diseases;
- Yellow fever;
- Zika virus disease.

3.2.1 Digital infrastructures and systems

3.2.1.1 Data sources

Standardised approach to PHPP intelligence gathering

When EU-HIP partners were asked whether they used a standardised approach to gather intelligence for the selected PHPP, ten out of fifteen countries reported that this was the case for all pathogens (Table 10). For the remaining countries, the absence of a standardised approach is mainly justified by the fact that surveillance of the pathogen(s) is not subject to compulsory notification (generally described by the legislation in place in the country). The pathogens most frequently cited as lacking a standardised approach among the consortium's countries are the Rift Valley fever virus (by 4 countries) and Chikungunya (by 2 countries).

¹⁰ Prioritizing diseases for research and development in emergency contexts - WHO

¹¹ Work Plan 2022 - HERA

¹² Pandemic preparedness and response: Host-pathogen interactions of infectious diseases with epidemic potential - Horizon Europe

Several countries mentioned using a standardized approach for all notifiable diseases in their countries¹³, but a different or additional surveillance is also in place for COVID-19 and/or influenza (e.g. an active micro surveillance, the inclusions of not only positive but also negative test results in the notification system, syndromic surveillance specific to acute respiratory symptoms, etc.).

Table 10: Standardised approach for intelligence gathering related to selected PHPP among the consortium MS.

	Number of countries reported
Standardised approach in place for all 11 pathogens of concern for which surveillance is performed	10/15 countries
Specific standardised approach for COVID-19 and/or influenza	7/15 countries

The standardised approach mentioned by countries may differ between pathogens within the same country, but also for the same pathogen the approach may differ between consortium MS. The standardised approach most frequently mentioned is the collection of laboratory data alone, sometimes requiring additional information from clinicians (primary care, hospitals, etc.).

Data sources used for intelligence gathering

There is a wide variety of data sources being used by different EU-HIP consortium countries for intelligence gathering on the selected PHPP. Overall, the pattern for data sources used is not very similar (Figure 3).

All countries reported having laboratory data as part of the surveillance for all the selected pathogens (when they are part of the notifiable diseases of the country). Overall, the most frequently reported data sources for the selected PHPP are hospitals, primary care and infectious disease registry data.

When relevant, a vaccine registry has been reported to be in place in ten countries for COVID-19 and in eight countries for influenza. Ten countries reported that they perform mortality monitoring for COVID-19 and influenza.

A particular feature is the monitoring of wastewater, which was reported by eleven countries as part of the COVID-19 monitoring programme. This source of information was mentioned by three countries for influenza.

Of all data sources, the least cited are nursing home surveillance data and Internet-based media data. Five countries mention specifically collected data from nursing homes for COVID-19, and two countries report using internet-based media data for the eleven pathogens of concern.

¹³ This phrase refers to a country's overall disease surveillance system. A country's notifiable diseases may not include the 11 pathogens selected for this project. Although countries may not have a standardised approach for one or more of the listed pathogens, they are included in this count by their express notification in the questionnaire that a standardised approach exists for their notifiable diseases.

Figure 3: Data sources used for intelligence gathering related to selected PHPP among consortium countries.

Additionally, several countries reported using disease vector surveillance data and contact tracing system data as a source of information for selected pathogens.

Level of data collection

All countries have indicated a national level collection for surveillance data of PHPP (Figure 4). Nine countries reported data collection at the regional level and seven at the local level for different pathogens. This more granular data collection was sometimes mentioned for data relating to COVID-19 and influenza only. It was highlighted by several countries that data on pathogens not subject to mandatory reporting were generally only collected at the national level.

Figure 4: Level of data collection for PHPP among the consortium countries.

Operational IT / digitized systems

All countries reported that operational IT/digitized systems are in place for PHPP, at least for COVID-19 and influenza. However, for most Member States, the IT/digitized systems are not limited to just these two pathogens. ~~All countries reported that operational IT/digitized systems are in place for PHPP, at least for COVID-19 and influenza, but often combined with other pathogens.~~ Nine out of fifteen countries indicated that an IT system is in place for all PHPP.

The questionnaire inquired whether IT systems are used for capturing signals, data analysis, reporting, and/or other purposes (Figure 5). All countries that answered this question, use their IT systems also for reporting purposes, at least partially towards the PHPPs they focus on. Six countries stated the use of operational IT/digitalized systems for signal capture, data analysis and reporting purposes for the eleven pathogens of concern. The availability of these three elements of disease monitoring through operational IT/digitalized systems was most reported for COVID-19 (by nine countries) and influenza (by eight countries). For other PHPP, the operational IT/digitalized systems in place are most frequently used for reporting purposes. Two of the consortium countries stated that they do not have an operational IT/digitized system in place for signal capture, data analysis and reporting for the selected PHPP other than COVID-19 and influenza.

At least eight countries reported operational IT/digitized systems for data analysis, and at least seven countries use them for capturing signals, towards the PHPP they focus on. Other reported uses include quality control and an integrated warning system.

Figure 5: Number of operational IT/digitalized systems in place mentioned regarding selected PHPP within consortium countries.

A related question included in the landscape analysis was on whether these operational IT / digitized systems offer functionalities for presenting or exporting data, such as Dashboards, reports, application programming interfaces (APIs) or Business Intelligence (BI) tools. All countries reported that this was the case for a minimum of one pathogen, predominantly

COVID-19. Seven countries reported that at least one type of these functionalities is offered for all PHPP.

Seven countries reported that they offer dashboards as a functionality. Three countries mentioned the use of APIs: there is limited use for COVID-19 in two countries, and it is under development for influenza in one country. Tools used to export/retrieve data have been reported to be available in four countries. Four countries mentioned using BI Tools, namely Power BI and SAP Business Objects, while one more country is in the process of adopting one.

Use of Artificial Intelligence in surveillance

One country reported that they currently use Artificial Intelligence (AI) in pathogen surveillance, and its application is limited only to COVID-19. AI tools are used in analyses (e.g. clustering, Principal Component Analysis plots) in both supervised and unsupervised spaces. AI is not used to pull signals to determine or suggest actions. All other countries reported that AI is not used and/or not considered for this task at the time of the questionnaire.

Data collection at designated Points of Entry

A Point of Entry (PoE) is a location where persons enter a country. This can be an entry by air (airport), sea (seaport) or land. A PoE is as such also a place where a PHPP can be introduced into the country. For that reason, the landscape analysis assessed whether countries perform data collection on PHPPs at designated PoE.

Two countries indicated that they currently collect data at specific points of entry for all PHPP (maritime, air and borders PoE), the designated PoE are integrated into both national surveillance systems.

Some countries indicated that they do not currently collect data at the PoE, but have done so in the past in the case of COVID-19 or during other specific crisis situations (filovirus or arenavirus epidemics with risk of entry). At the same time they indicated that PoE data collection will be put in place in case of crisis situations.

Several European actions have been taken in relation to the specific case of surveillance at the PoE. The Joint Action on preparedness and action at points of entry (ports, airports, and ground crossings), *Healthy GateWays*, was undertaken from 2018 to 2021. This project aimed to improve coordinated cross-sectoral actions to control infectious disease transmission and possible vectors for pathogens on different modes of transportations. The projects' final results are available¹⁴. The SHARP Joint Action (Strengthening International Health Regulations and Preparedness in the EU) also focused on strengthening member's existing capacities and supporting improvements related to International Health Regulations for PoE¹⁵.

3.2.1.2 Data linkage and data sharing

Data linkage

A unique personal identifier (UPIN) is an identifier (e.g., code or number) that uniquely identifies a patient/citizen within a healthcare system or database. The use of a unique personal identifier allows linkage of data across different databases, as well as following up individuals longitudinally.

¹⁴ EU HEALTHY GATEWAYS - Joint Action Preparedness and Action at points of entry (ports, airports, ground crossings)

¹⁵ Strengthening IHR capacities for Point of Entry - SHARP Joint Action (sharpja.eu)

All countries use a UPIN for monitoring at least one of the selected pathogens (Table 11). Ten countries use the same UPIN across all the selected pathogens, while five use a UPIN only for some pathogens.

The type of UPIN varies across countries, and some countries use several types of UPIN. The majority of countries (11 out of 15) use a social security number or national identification number. Five countries use a health-specific number (e.g., health system number, health insurance number, hospital record number). Finally, five countries noted that they use case/notification numbers. Three countries reported using sample identification numbers allowing linkage to samples and laboratory results.

Table 11: Type of UPIN used for the surveillance of the selected PHPP among consortium MS.

	Social security / National ID number	Health-specific personal identification number	Case number	Unique sample ID	WGS* identifier
Number of countries reported	11	5	5	3	1

*Whole Genome Sequencing

Data sharing

Regarding sharing data with international organisations, all countries send data to ECDC via EpiPulse/TESSy and almost all to the Early Warning and Response System (EWRS). In addition, several countries reported that they send data to different data collection systems of the WHO, such as the WHO Joint Reporting Form, Global Influenza Surveillance and Response System, Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources.

One Health networks and collaborations

Countries are involved with One Health networks or collaborations, including through collaboration with international organisations, involvement in projects or Joint Actions, and exchanging data on One Health. Among the larger initiatives and projects mentioned were One Health European Joint Programme (One Health -EJP) that was coordinated by ANSES in France, and the UNITED4Surveillance Joint Action that is coordinated by RIVM in the Netherlands (Table 12).

Table 12: Involvement of consortium countries in One Health networks and collaborations

	Number of consortium countries reported
Collaboration with international organisations ⁽¹⁾	10
One Health-related projects/initiatives ⁽²⁾	10
One Health-related data collection ⁽³⁾	3

⁽¹⁾ As examples: Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), WHO, ECDC, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

⁽²⁾ As examples: One Health European Joint Programme (One Health EJP), UNITED4Surveillance, Preventing Zoonotic Disease Emergence (PREZODE) Initiative, Joint Action on Antimicrobial Resistance (JAMRAI-2), One Health living lab

⁽³⁾ As examples: Global Burden of Animal Diseases, Yearly zoonosis report, GLASS

3.2.1.3 Data storage

Eight countries reported a national IT infrastructure in place for the storage and processing of health data for the surveillance system(s) targeting the eleven pathogens of concern. For the remaining countries, the absence of IT structures is justified through various reasons: no cases have been detected yet, the disease is not classified as endemic in the country (few cases or imported ones) or the regulations in place may (or may not) require the notification of cases, but not necessarily their storage and process through an IT infrastructure.

All of the fifteen countries reported a national IT infrastructure in place for the storage and process of health data for COVID-19 and influenza surveillance systems.

Four countries reported to have or planning to set up a secure cloud for healthcare data related to the pathogens. COVID-19 is the only one disease for which two countries, in addition to those mentioned above, notified that they have or are planning to set up a secure cloud for health data.

3.2.1.4 Standards and data quality

Use of standards

Standardization refers to the acceptance of specifications (e.g. definitions, norms, rules) that establishes a common language as a basis for understanding and exchange of information between different parties. Standardized terminologies in healthcare are aimed to provide a foundation for interoperability between health information systems, enhancing accuracy, reliability and comparability of health information at local, regional, national and international levels¹⁶.

The aim of standardising disease capture is to report information according to criteria in order to have a harmonized data collection and a unified national epidemiological surveillance.

Ten countries reported using standardized forms and templates for data capture and/or reporting for the whole list of selected PHPP.

Data capture can be done through a general IT system in place for all communicable diseases reporting, directly notified by physicians and laboratories personnel. More regularly, data capture is made through a template form sent by physicians of laboratories personnel to Public Health authorities, the standardized forms or template can be developed for a specific pathogens family (e.g. respiratory illness and pathogens), a specific surveillance system (e.g. GP sentinel network) or a specific illness/pathogen alone.

Seven countries reported ICD-10 as the only standardised terminology used for diseases classification, while the eight other consortium countries mentioned using different standardized terminologies for health-related information, either definitions provided by international health organisations or national adaptations of these same clinical case definitions. Table 13 shows the different terminologies mostly used within the consortium countries, in the area of PHPP.

¹⁶ eHealth: standardized terminology - Report by the Secretariat. WHO (2006)

Table 13: Standardized terminologies mostly used in PHPP surveillance among consortium MS.

	ICD-10 ⁽¹⁾	LOINC ⁽²⁾	NPU ⁽³⁾	SNOMED-CT ⁽⁴⁾
Number of countries reported	13	6	2	3

⁽¹⁾ ICD-10 is the 10th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Disease and Related Health Problem (ICD), a WHO medical classification list for clinical terms and diagnoses to record statistics on diseases (signs and symptoms, abnormal findings, complaints, social circumstances, and external causes of injury) in primary, secondary and tertiary care, as well as on cause of death certificates.

⁽²⁾ Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes (LOINC) is a common language (set of identifiers, names, and codes) for identifying Laboratory and Clinical tests, measurements and observations.

⁽³⁾ The Nomenclature, Properties and Units (NPU) terminology is a coding system and terminology for identification and communication of examination results from clinical laboratories in the health area. It identifies types of result values, for use in reporting laboratory results.

⁽⁴⁾ The Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED-CT) is a comprehensive clinical health terminology, encoding the meanings of terms often used in healthcare settings, such as symptoms, signs, diagnoses, procedures, clinical findings, and body structures. Its database is also able to distinguish between aetiologies, pharmaceuticals, specimens, and medical devices.

Within the consortium, it was noted that the use of different terminologies did not always serve the same purpose (e.g. SNOMED CT terminology may be used in one country only for laboratory results and will be used as vaccines terminology in another). No clear pattern was observed through the analysis of the questionnaire.

In addition, three countries indicated that they are in the process of aligning with the SNOMED-CT standard.

Data transfers

Eight countries reported the occurrence of data transfers from different data providers to a centralized health database at the national level, and/or data linkage between different databases. Three countries reported that this type of transfer or linkage was only carried out for data concerning COVID-19 and influenza; one country reported the availability of these processes only for data relating to COVID-19. Three countries mentioned that no data transfers from different providers to a centralized health database at the national level or data linkage between databases are processed for the eleven pathogens of concern.

Metadata catalogue

A metadata catalogue is a structured and organized repository or database that stores information about various data assets within an organization. The catalogue serves as a centralized resource for managing metadata, enabling efficient data governance, search and retrieval across diverse datasets.

Seven countries among the consortium countries mentioned the availability of a metadata catalogue, but no clear pattern regarding this availability was seen. Four countries reported having a metadata catalogue available for the eleven pathogens of concern. Other countries notified the availability of a metadata catalogue for specific pathogens. Six countries reported that they did not have a metadata catalogue for the eleven PHPP.

Regularity of input and response

Regular data collection and reporting enables ongoing monitoring of pathogens and their impact on the population. One of the key strategic objectives reported by the WHO¹⁷ is to strengthen real-time data collection systems and genomic surveillance of SARS-CoV-2 and other pathogens with epidemic and pandemic potential. In this review, the reporting to international organization has not been included the subject is covered in “Data sharing”.

Countries reported regular input of data for COVID-19 and influenza, from a daily to a weekly data collection schedule. The information collected corresponds, for both pathogens, mainly to the number of confirmed cases, number of tests performed and deaths. For the other PHPP, there is no similar regular data collection. The collection of data will commonly start by an ad-hoc notification by practitioners of unusual symptoms (Table 14).

Table 14: Frequency of data input for the selected PHPP among consortium countries.

	Daily	Daily to Weekly	Weekly	Ad-hoc
COVID-19	6	7	2	0
Influenza	4	3	8	
Other pathogens	0	0	0	15

The frequency of response activities for COVID-19 and influenza is primarily on a weekly schedule, involving weekly reports, with occasional daily information reporting through dashboards. The reported information mostly concerned number of GP consultations, the laboratory-confirmed cases, hospital and ICU admissions, genomic or virological surveillance, vaccination and wastewater surveillance.

For the other PHPP, information is mainly reported annually or monthly as part of reports on notifiable diseases or reports on communicable/infectious diseases (Table 15).

Table 15: Frequency of PHPP response activities

	Daily to Weekly	Weekly	Monthly	Yearly
COVID-19	4	11	0	0
Influenza	1	13	0	1
Other pathogens	0	0	4	9

3.2.1.5 Threat indicators

Threat detection plays a crucial role in effective surveillance of PHPP by enabling early identification and data-driven decision-making to mitigate the impact of emerging infectious diseases. Countries employ diverse methodologies and tools to detect threats, depending on the resources and technologies available (Table 16).

¹⁷ STRATEGIC PREPAREDNESS AND RESPONSE PLAN : APRIL 2023 – APRIL 2025 - From emergency response to long-term covid-19 disease management: sustaining gains made during the covid-19 pandemic. WHO

Table 16: Threat detection methods for the selected PHPP among consortium countries.

	Event-based ⁽¹⁾	Indicator-based ⁽²⁾	Syndromic surveillance ⁽³⁾	Threshold ⁽⁴⁾
COVID-19	8	11	6	5
Influenza	8	9	7	5
Lassa, CCH, Ebola and Marburg fevers	12	7	2	2
MERS and SARS	11	(6)	3	2
Rift Valley fever	10	6	(3)	2
Yellow fever, Dengue, Zika and Chikungunya	11	(7)	2	2

() occurrence counted but may not concern the entire list of pathogens cited in the line for one or more countries

⁽¹⁾ Event-based detection is the organised and rapid capture of information about events that are a potential risk to public health, referring to a method of monitoring and tracking the occurrence of specific health-related events in a population. Health authorities and medical practitioners actively collect and analyse data on specific events, such as cases of illness, hospital admissions or deaths.

⁽²⁾ Indicator-based is the systematic (regular) collection, monitoring and analysis and interpretation of structured data, to track specific health-related indicators such as incidence or prevalence rates in a population. Health authorities collect and analyse data on specific indicators such as the number of cases of a specific disease, the incidence of hospital admissions or the prevalence of a risk factor.

⁽³⁾ Syndromic surveillance entails tracking patterns of symptoms or syndromes (clusters of symptoms) in the population. This can provide early indications of unusual health events before a specific diagnosis is confirmed.

⁽⁴⁾ The threshold method involves establishing predefined criteria or thresholds that trigger a response when surpassed. These criteria could be based on specific epidemiological indicators, such as the number of cases, transmission rate, or severity of illness. Once the predetermined threshold is met or exceeded, appropriate actions are initiated to address the identified threat.

The proportion of expert involvement varies from pathogen to pathogen. Only a few countries, and for specific pathogens, have an automatic or partially automatic system in place for the detection of threats.

Validation is defined as a process of verifying the authenticity and accuracy of a threat (answering the question whether the detected signal is indeed a public health threat signal/event/threat) by cross-checking the information with multiple sources and conducting additional investigation as needed. Within the countries involved, the validation and assessment of a threat is performed with the involvement of experts.

3.2.2 Legislative aspects

In terms of legislation, in addition to the EU health security framework including the International Health Regulations (IHR) and the Regulation (EU) 2022/2371 on serious cross-border threats to health, countries have national legislation relating to pandemic preparedness and surveillance of pathogens with high pandemic potential. EU regulations only provide a general framework whereas detailed authorizations and obligations are stipulated in national regulations. These regulations include nominations of public health authorities, accreditation of laboratories, reporting obligations of healthcare providers etc.

Annex 3 includes a table listing the relevant legislations for health emergency preparedness, surveillance of pathogens with high pandemic potential, and health data sharing.

In terms of pandemic preparedness plans, most countries (12 out of 15) have a pandemic preparedness plan for at least some pathogens. Many countries are in the process of updating their pandemic preparedness plans or drafting plans for new pathogens. More details per country can be seen in Annex 3.

When asked whether the legislation providing the legal framework is up to date, seven countries indicated that the legislation is up to date for all of the eleven pathogens of concern, while seven countries stated that the legislation requires updates for at least some pathogens. Several countries indicated that such updates are underway (Table 17). Most countries (11 out of 15) have up to date legislation on COVID-19.

Table 17: Up-to-date legislation regarding the PHPP selected list within the consortium MS.

	Yes, for all pathogens*	Yes, for some pathogens*	No, for all pathogens*
Number of countries reported	7	5	2

* are only considered the eleven PHPP of concern

Agreements for sharing data

Most countries (11 out of 15) reported that they have agreements in place for sharing data among national stakeholders and regions. Among them, eight countries reported having agreements in place for the selected PHPP, and three countries only have such agreements for some pathogens. Two countries mentioned not having agreements in place for sharing data among stakeholders and regions.

Regarding data sharing with other countries and international organisations, data reporting related to outbreak and as part of rapid communication systems to the ECDC and WHO are formalised under EU legislation and the IHR. Sharing of data on novel or emerging infections (including pandemic influenza) through the Early Warning and Response System (EWRS) is regulated at European level by Regulation (EU) 2022/2371 on serious cross-border threats to health.

Five countries noted that they have agreements for sharing data internationally only for some pathogens. Table 18 below outlines the responses received on agreements to share data internationally.

Table 18: Agreement for sharing data internationally among the consortium countries in regard to the selected PHPP.

	Yes, for all pathogens*	Yes, for some pathogens*	No, for all pathogens*
Number of countries reported	8	5	1

Some countries reported 'none'

* the eleven PHPP of concern

3.2.3 Key actors and stakeholder's network

The table in annex 3 provides an overview of the main stakeholders per country concerning pathogens with high pandemic potential. Where feasible, their responsibilities are delineated per pathogen, offering insight into the collaborative efforts and division of responsibilities among key actors in pandemic preparedness and response efforts in the country. Understanding the roles and contributions of these stakeholders is crucial for effective coordination and mitigation strategies in the face of emerging infectious threats.

The various stakeholders concerning pathogens with high pandemic potential and their respective roles in different consortium member countries include the following institutions and organizations:

- **Ministries and central government authorities** handle crisis preparedness, formulate and implement strategies and regulations, provide political oversight and legislation, manage finances, declare and manage health emergencies, and coordinate between ministries.
- **Public health institutions** are responsible for epidemiology, surveillance, vaccine effectiveness control, national coordination, Risk Assessment Group coordination, communication during cross-border health threats, operation of national reference labs, and provision of guidance.
- **Laboratories** perform testing and collect information on positive and negative laboratory test results.
- **Hospitals** gather data on hospitalizations, operate reference hospitals, conduct genomic surveillance, and provide diagnostics and treatment.
- **Regional and local health authorities** oversee vaccine roll-out, own vaccination data, enforce mandatory notification, conduct risk assessment and contact tracing, perform disease surveillance, promote health, prevent diseases, and coordinate responses.
- **Universities and research institutions** organize vaccination campaigns, offer recommendations on vaccination strategy, and collect data from primary care settings.
- **Medicine agencies** regulate medicinal products, ensure medicine safety, including pathogen surveillance.
- **Other stakeholders** address e.g. patient safety, manage contact tracing, implement local public health measures and guidance, and combat biological threats while supporting preparedness and knowledge enhancement at the national level.

3.3 Chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear threats (CBRN)

Most EU-HIP consortium countries reported to monitor CBRN threats, similarly as other health threats. Work related to detection, mitigation and management of CBRN threats involves a wide range of activities: monitoring and early detection of unusual patterns of illnesses or symptoms that may indicate a CBRN event, establishment of protocols for responding to CBRN incidents, including medical treatment and evacuation plans, collection and analysis of environmental samples to identify the presence of hazardous substances, development of communication strategies to inform the public and stakeholders during emergencies.

3.3.1 Digital infrastructures and systems

Data sources used for intelligence gathering

Several sources of data are used for intelligence gathering purposes related to CBRN health threats, for example laboratory data, hospital, nursing home and primary care data, wastewater monitoring, mortality monitoring, internet-based media, infectious disease registries. Several early warning/signaling networks, including international alert systems, are dealing with intelligence gathering on either C, B, R, N or a combination of these. The information is gathered from several sources and stakeholders, including e.g. data from radiation early warning systems, border guards' services, fire and rescue department, police etc.

Six countries reported using a standardized approach to public health intelligence gathering and an equal number reported that in the case of biological threats it depends on the pathogen, with different organizations responsible for different threats.

Most countries collect data at multiple levels (national, regional, provincial or local level). Five countries have data collection at designated points of entry (PoEs, e.g., airports, border crossings) and the designated PoEs are integrated into the national surveillance system.

Operational IT / digitized systems

Nine countries report that an operational IT/ digitized system is in place for one or more of the domains – chemical, biological, radiological and nuclear, while one of the surveyed countries reported lacking such a system. There are early warning networks in place and also general incident management portals, international tools and signals capture systems in use.

Indicator-based and event-based surveillance are applied to CBRN threats. Information from different sources is constantly gathered, filtered, analyzed and reported in terms of identification of risks, alerts and potential emergencies. Responsibility is shared amongst several actors and various authorities.

Functionalities to present and export data are relatively limited. The systems of six countries support at least some reporting functionalities such as dashboards, reports, APIs (Application Programming Interface), and various Business Intelligence tools (Qlik, Power Bi, Tableau, Google Data Studio etc.)

AI solutions are not employed in national systems or considered at the moment, with the exception of one country.

3.3.1.1 Data linkage and data sharing

A unique personal identifier (UPIN) is not generally used for data storage and linkage (reported by only two countries).

Five countries reported data transfers from different data providers (e.g. different laboratories) to a centralized health database or data space at the national level, and/or data linkage between different databases. There is regular (weekly, monthly or yearly) input of data (data updates) and response activities in eight countries.

Ten countries share data with relevant EU and other international organizations and/or other EU Member States. Countries are using different portals, platforms, web services, Early Warning Systems and networks.

A secure cloud for healthcare data is not common, it was mentioned to be in place or planned in two countries.

3.3.1.2 Standards and data quality

Standardized forms and templates for data/information capture and reporting are in place in seven countries, while standardized terminologies are used in four countries in their data sources supporting public health surveillance and related data management. A metadata catalogue for CBRN public health surveillance data sources is available in three countries.

3.3.1.3 Threat indicators

Detection of potential health threats is primarily event based (reported by 10 countries), while also indicator(s)-based (5 countries), threshold based and syndromic (both mentioned by three countries) or other means of surveillance were reported.

Threat detection, as well as threat assessment and validation are not performed purely automatically, rather they usually require the involvement of one or more experts.

3.3.2 Legislative aspects

Agreements for sharing data are common, with ten countries reporting sharing data among national stakeholders and regions.

Eight countries reported that there are agreements in the countries for sharing data with other countries and international organizations.

The legal framework supporting CBRN-related activities is reported as up to date by six countries, while two countries responded that their legislation is not up to speed. Seven countries have related preparedness plans, or there are plans to develop them.

3.3.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network

The table in Annex 4 provides an overview of the main stakeholders at country-level concerning CBRN. Understanding the roles and contributions of these stakeholders is crucial for effective coordination and mitigation strategies in the face of emerging CBRN threats.

The various stakeholders concerning CBRN in different consortium member countries include the following institutions and organizations:

- Ministries of various government sectors including internal affairs, health and social affairs, defense, foreign affairs, finance, economy and employment, agriculture
- Emergency experts and local authorities
- Border Guards
- Defence Forces
- Institutes
- Information Centres
- Crisis Management Centres
- Safety Authorities
- Customs
- Laboratories
- Steering Committees
- Advisory Boards
- Coordination units
- Environment Authorities
- Universities
- Competent authorities for internal events
- Municipalities
- Other directorates and entities

3.4 Medical Countermeasures (MCM)

The work of EU-HIP on Medical countermeasures (MCM) used the definition provided under Article 3 of the Regulation on serious cross-border threats to health and repealing Decision No 1082/2013/EU (SCBTH), i.e., medicinal products for human use and medical devices or other goods or services for the purpose of preparedness and response to a serious cross-border threat to health. This definition includes:

- Medicinal products, including vaccines,
- Medical devices, including in vitro diagnostic devices,
- Personal Protective Equipment, disinfectants etc.
- Other relevant products (e.g. substances of human origin).

During the data collection work, it was noted that in some countries also a different definition and grouping of MCM is in use: "...medicines and medical supplies that can be used to diagnose, prevent, or treat diseases related to chemical, biological, radiological, or nuclear (CBRN) threats. MCM can include:

- Biologic products – vaccines, blood products, and antibodies.
- Drugs – antimicrobial or antiviral drugs
- Devices – diagnostic tests to identify threat agents and personal protective equipment (PPE)"

Even though the definitions are not per se conflicting, this sort of terminology and grouping variations are important to acknowledge, due to eventual possible impact on interoperability.

The area of MCM was addressed by an accordingly tailored section of the EU-HIP questionnaire. Although the general structure applied in other topic areas was maintained in terms of key domains of interest (i.e., digital infrastructure, key stakeholders and legal framework) the MCM part of the questionnaire included also topic-specific themes such as stockpiling.

3.4.1 Digital infrastructures and systems

Our investigation of the MCM landscape begun from the availability of general digital infrastructure supporting MCM-related activities. According to the responses received, almost half of EU-HIP-consortium countries report the presence of a digitized system for MCM. The mentioned systems may be in various stages of development and maturity, as well as coverage of the MCM domain.

Digital data collection on MCM

Having established an indication of the extent of digitized systems used in the MCM area, we aimed for a more specific picture of their coverage for each MCM category. The degree to which data and information on MCM different categories is digitized (incl. the needed underlying infrastructure) is crucial for EU-level monitoring and preparedness activities to work. The respective information can be viewed as a crude indicator of readiness to support such activities and, conversely, of the existing gap to be covered by development activities, primarily on the national level – an area being addressed by the activities of WP5.

Not surprisingly, medicinal products and medical devices appear to be the most addressed MCM categories, with PPE following rather closely.

Figure 6: Coverage of MCM categories in digital systems among consortium countries

Systems for data collection – Medicinal products

There is a variety of systems employed for MCM-related data collection.

Table 19. Examples of systems employed for MCM data collection among some of the EU-HIP consortium countries

COUNTRY	SYSTEM
BELGIUM	<p>PharmaStatus application: it provides information on availability of medicines in Belgium, including those currently on the market, recently marketed medicines, both for human and veterinary use. The application indicates when medicines are newly introduced, temporarily unavailable, back in stock, or when their marketing has been temporarily or permanently stopped. Patients can use the platform to check the availability of their medications and sign up to receive updates on the specific availability of a particular medicine. Marketing authorization holders can use the application to report start, temporary unavailability or discontinuation of a medicine directly to the FAMHP. Pharmacists and wholesaler distributors can also communicate directly with the marketing authorization holder through the application, if they suspect a medicine is wrongly marked as “available” on the PharmaStatus website or if the presumed end date for a temporary unavailability has passed.</p> <p>The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (INAMI/RIZIV) is tasked with the management of health insurance in Belgium and the collection of data pertaining to the usage and costs of medicines. https://pharmastatus.be/about</p>
FINLAND	<p>The Finnish Medicines Agency (FIMEA) ensures, from development to use, the quality, safety and efficacy of medicines for human and veterinary use, pharmacy made and officinal preparations, of health products, including medical devices and accessories, and raw materials for the preparation and production of medicines and of all operations involving blood, cells and tissues, which are also defined as health products. FIMEA maintains a database of registered medical devices and oversees the approval process for new devices before they can be placed on the market.</p> <p>The Social Insurance institution (Kela) is responsible for managing health insurance in Finland and collects data related to the use and costs of medicines. Kela is responsible for maintaining the national patient archive including ePrescription and eDispensation services. The archive contains information on all medication prescribed and dispensed through pharmacies in Finland but lacks information on medication used in hospital setting.</p> <p>The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) is responsible for maintaining national health care registers for primary and secondary care including both the public and private sector. Registries contain information on medication used and prescribed. The delay is up to 7 days in primary care and up to 30 days in secondary care.</p> <p>The National Emergency Supply Agency (NESA) is responsible for stockpiling emergency supplies including PPE.</p> <p>THL and NESA are jointly responsible for operating RescEU stockpile on CBRN threats where THL is responsible for medication and NESA is responsible for supplies.</p>
FRANCE	<p>A computerized system for managing exceptional health situations, with the aim of managing tactical stocks in healthcare establishments. This system inventories existing data (database, Excel files, paper traceability), identifies the tactical supplies held and reconciles the establishment’s product codes with the product codes in the national repository.</p> <p>Tactical resources management tool (SIGESSE) is a shared computerized tool for managing tactical resources deployed in hospitals.</p>

<p>GERMANY</p>	<p>The Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Device, the Paul-Ehrlich-Institute, the Federal Institute for Vaccines and Biomedicines, and other relevant authorities in Germany assess risks and safety warnings related to medical devices and issue safety warnings when safety problems or quality deficiencies are identified, as well as research, evaluation and approval of biomedicines for human use and immunological veterinary medicinal products. Germany has a pharmacovigilance system that covers the recording and analysis of side effects and quality problems with pharmaceuticals. This system detects potential problems in the supply chain of pharmaceuticals and there are threshold values for reporting side effects. There are also early warning systems based on monitoring data and information from manufacturers. If a potential supply shortage is detected, appropriate measures can be initiated to ensure the availability of MCMs. Safety warnings and recalls can be issued in the event of quality or safety issues with MCM. These measures are taken when certain threshold values are reached or exceeded.</p>
<p>ICELAND</p>	<p>Medicines in general, IMA can request data of stocks from distributors. Emergency medicines stock owned by the Chief Epidemiologist, can request data from manager of stocks (at Landspítali hospital). PPE stockpiling not digitalized. Medical devices stocks not digitalized or registered. A central database for inventory of medicines and medical equipment in the country does not exist, however, it is possible to request the inventory status of medicines from pharmaceutical wholesalers if necessary (by the IMA). Medicines need the approval of the medicines agencies before marketing, and therefore there is a good overview of marketed medicines and their inventory can be requested, as mentioned. Regarding medical devices, the approval of medicines agencies / appropriate authorities is not required prior to marketing, and therefore an accurate status of the number and types of medical devices in the country is challenging.</p> <p>Currently, there is an amendment before Parliament on the law on the inventory of medicines and medical equipment, which attempts to ensure that the Icelandic Medicines Agency (IMA) can keep a central database of the actual (real-time) inventory of medicines and medical equipment. However, there is a large degree of uncertainty that the proposal will succeed in the format proposed.</p>
<p>ITALY</p>	<p>There are several laws and regulations relating to medical countermeasures. For the monitoring of distribution, reference is made to the Central Data Bank governed by the Decree of the Minister of Health of 15 July 2004. The regulation of the methods of registration in the database and in the Directory of Medical Devices is provided by the Decree of 21 December 2009, supplemented with reference to in vitro diagnostics by the Decree of 23 December 2013.</p> <p>At the national level, the collection of data on the health services supply network was established by the Decree of the Minister of Health of 5 December 2006. Monitoring and bed occupancy indicators are implemented on the basis of an Italian Circular in application of the Ministerial Decree of 6 March 2023.</p>
<p>NORWAY</p>	<p>Vaccines are stored centrally In Norway under the responsibility of the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH). Information about vaccines is kept in a warehouse management system at NIPH. No export of data. The main indicator registered centrally on vaccines is vaccination status per inhabitant and coverage for population done by the Norwegian Immunisation Registry SYSVAK. Sales of vaccines is reported annually to NIPH (https://www.fhi.no/en/he/drug/om-den-grossistbaserte-legemiddelforbruksstatistikken/)</p> <p>For medical products, NoMA medicine database only collects volume data on an ad-hoc basis for medicinal products, when for example wholesaler stock data is needed in assessment of shortage situations. Norwegian Prescribed Drug Registry is a health register with information on medicines dispensed by prescription from pharmacies (https://www.fhi.no/va/sysvak/), (https://www.fhi.no/he/legemiddelregisteret/) (https://www.legemiddelsok.no/sider/english.aspx)</p>

Type of digital information collected – Medicinal products

The actual information areas covered for each MCM category is a key question in establishing and promoting interoperability across platforms. Table 20 demonstrates the distribution across various standard elements, using the area of medicinal products as the example. Information on the available quantity tops the list, followed by Name and Manufacturer (of the product).

Table 20: Data categories for Medicinal products documentation employed across EU-HIP-consortium countries

--

Reviewing MCM stockpiling status

According to the ATHINA glossary, **MCM preparedness** “means the capability to make MCM accessible i.e., to manufacture, procure, purchase, stockpile, and distribute MCM, in order to rapidly respond to a health threat”. Hence collection of data on the status of MCM stockpiling in participating countries is another important piece in understanding the respective landscape.

In the same glossary, **stockpile management** is meant as reference “...to the ability for the ATHINA platform to provide an efficient overview of stockpile information from producers and Member States (virtual and physical) on crisis-relevant raw materials.

Moreover, it should provide information on **procurements** and **reserves** of medical countermeasures (including therapeutics and vaccines) capacities at EU level, thereby easing the management and deployment of these capacities.”

Therefore EU-HIP attempted to map the digital tools and systems in use for managing stockpile information and – to some extent – the status of the present stockpile reserves.

Preparing for public health emergencies

Consortium participant countries were inquired concerning the availability of national medical countermeasures stockpiles for use during a public health emergency. As shown in Figure 7, the category of MCM mostly reported in stockpile were PPE – perhaps a reflection of COVID-19 pandemic proximity – with medicines and medical devices following up.

Figure 7: National stockpile availability per MCM category

Additional details concerning national stockpiles are shown in Table 21.

Table 21. Types of national stockpiles and responsible bodies in some of the EU-HIP-consortium countries

COUNTRY	NATIONAL STOCKPILES
BELGIUM	As of May 2022, the Strategic Pharmaceutical Stock Platform (PSPS) has been established. It has members from the Ministry of Defense, FAMHP, the FPS, and other relevant stakeholders. The Minister of Public Health has assigned the PSPS the responsibility of creating a priority list for the formation of the strategic pharmaceutical stock, specifically addressing the potential threats of chemical, biological, and radiological terrorism, as well as pandemic threats. BE Health Emergency Preparedness 17/01/2023 FR SPF Santé publique (belgium.be) https://news.belgium.be/fr/developpement-du-stock-federal-pharmaceutique-strategique
CROATIA	Information classified. Responsible body is the Commodity Inventories as an administrative organization within the Ministry for the Economy. In the latest update of the Croatian Law on Strategic Products MCM including vaccines and essential medicines have been included and are currently being stockpiled.

FINLAND	THL's medicinal product wholesale takes care of the availability of vaccines, antibodies and research materials needed to combat certain dangerous or rare infectious diseases. In addition, THL acquires and distributes the vaccines of the national vaccination program. Parliament allocates the necessary funds for this every year and THL delivers the vaccines of the national vaccination program free of charge to the medical center or hospital pharmacy in the welfare area. As part of the rescEU project, emergency stocks are being built to prepare for chemical (C), biological (B), radioactivity (R) and nuclear material (N) accidents and disruptions in Europe. Emergency stocks are also used to prepare for pandemics such as COVID-19, as well as malfunctions of medicines and protective equipment or their depletion in member countries due to, for example, a terrorist attack or the use of military force. THL is responsible for the procurement and storage of medicinal products.
FRANCE	Antivirals, antidotes, vaccines, iodine tablets, anaesthesia, cardiovascular, electrolytes, antiseptics, thermal shock blanket, bandages, contention, stitches
GERMANY	Medication, vaccines, blood storage, consumables
ICELAND	No stockpiling for medical equipment. The Chief Epidemiologist has a stockpile of minimal essential medicines and distributors are responsible for keeping an inventory of a one-month supply (one-month supply as defined by the usage of the Landspítali – National University Hospital). This list of essential medicines is defined by a Regulation No 212/2012 supported by Act No 19/1997 but compiled by the Chief Epidemiologist in collaboration with specialists at the hospital. The stockpile is managed by the Landspítali Hospital and the list is currently under review as it is over 10 years old. Vaccines are separate and the Chief Epidemiologist's stock of vaccines is kept by the distributors as per contracts. The Chief Epidemiologist also holds a stockpile of PPE but the database is not digital yet.
LITHUANIA	Stockpiles available (no additional information)
NORWAY	Norway has established stockpiles for vaccines and important medicines. This includes both medicines that are critical in situations of health crisis, and daily use medicines that are important to avoid a potential health crisis (e.g pain tablets, antibiotics). https://www.sjukehusapoteka-vest.no/49999a5/siteassets/seksjon/nasjonaltberedskapslager/documents/b180--nasjonalt-beredskapslager-for-legemidler-pr.-02.2023.pdf
PORTUGAL	Antivirals for influenza, COVID-19 and mpox
ROMANIA	Stockpiles available
SLOVENIA	Stockpiles available (no additional information)

Resilience of the stockpiling supply-chain

We also attempted to assess the resilience of MCM stockpile supply-chains by requesting information on the existence of suitable processes to identify potential issues, risks, stockpiling bottlenecks, disruption and vulnerabilities. A follow up question investigated further the degree of automation of MCM stockpile supply chains (*automated system and a threshold set for MCM supply-chain issue identification*), as well as possible utilization of AI or BI solutions.

Figure 8: Processes for identifying MCM supply-chain issues

Unsurprisingly, the majority of positive responses concerned the category of medicinal products, with seven of the consortium partner countries indicating the presence of monitoring practices. Automation of problem detection appears to still be in an early phase, with only five out of the seven responding positively to the question of automated solutions use for supply-chain problems identification. Furthermore, amongst the queried countries, six indicated the use of AI-driven solutions or similar to manage stockpile quantities.

International MCM data reporting and sharing

In addition to acquiring a baseline understanding of the MCM digital landscape across consortium partner countries, it is of the essence to explore the practices concerning exchange and mutual utilization of MCM data on the national and EU level.

As Figure 9 indicates, international reporting and sharing of MCM data with other Member States and/or EU organizations was reported by almost half of consortium members and concerns primarily medicinal products and MDDs.

Responses to the question on monitoring effectiveness and impact of deployed MCM in the context of a major crisis related to the threats relevant for HERA indicate that there is still room for improvement in benefiting from digital infrastructures: four countries reported utilizing the MCM IT-systems for medicinal products in this respect, and two countries IT-systems on medical devices and PPE. Given the amount of missing information, as well as the sensitivity of the topic, this is just a tentative observation.

Figure 9: Data reporting and sharing w/ other Member States and EU-organisations per MCM category

3.4.2 Legislative aspects

For preparedness activities to be effective, coordination and information sharing among complex and multifaceted national and international networks are required. We attempted to outline the state of national readiness, by inquiring also on the practices of data sharing among national and regional stakeholders in the area of MCM.

We received a total of four negative responses, while responses were missing from another seven countries. Among the examples provided by some of the EU-HIP consortium countries, Iceland indicated that in the area of MCM the data exchange is based on the Act on Health Security and Communicable Diseases and informal agreements and is operating within the limitations introduced by the GDPR, while in Portugal data sharing is only activated in cases of alerts and emergencies.

In Finland, the sharing of data between the regional and national level is implemented as part of the national preparedness framework; the national state of MCM preparedness is monitored and coordinated at the national level by the advisory board on states of emergency (PONK) under the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health (MSAH) and its committees on e.g. MCM and material logistics. THL collects data on preparedness and capabilities from the well-being services counties to support the work of the committees and MSAH.

MCM and preparedness plans

We aimed to understand MCM data sharing in the wider context of national preparedness plans and at least presently the emerging picture indicates that the domain of MCM requires strengthening, with only three of the EU-HIP consortium countries reporting on the existence of an MCM preparedness plan.

Status of MCM pertinent legal framework

The ability of various stakeholders, as well as the requirements placed on them in order to operate in the MCM area are largely determined by the existing legal framework. EU-HIP did

not attempt an exhaustive mapping or analysis of the legal framework, rather we requested of consortium partners to give us an indication of the key legal instruments in the domain – at least from their perspective – as well as assess whether the current legal framework around MCM is up to date or an update would be in order.

Four responding countries supported explicitly the view that the MCM-pertinent legislation is up to date, while an equal number of countries were explicitly of the opinion that revisions are needed. The remaining countries either did not take a stand at the time of inquiry or their responses were missing.

The table below gives an overview of legal instruments relevant for MCM activities, as identified across the EU-HIP consortium.

Table 22: Overview of MCM-related legal instruments examples provided by EU-HIP-consortium countries

COUNTRY	LEGISLATION FOR MCM
BELGIUM	BE Health Emergency Preparedness 17/01/2023 FR SPF Santé publique (belgium.be)
CROATIA	As of December of 2022 a law was enforced (Law on strategic commodity stocks) to include medicines in the stockpiling strategy, but it is not yet fully implemented. MDDs not included in stockpiling but efforts are ongoing.
DENMARK	Legislation is up to date for MCM (no additional information)
FINLAND	<p>National legislation regarding medicines https://www.fimea.fi/web/en/supervision/legislation/national_laws and administrative regulations https://www.fimea.fi/web/en/supervision/legislation/administrative_regulations</p> <p>National legislation related to medical devices https://www.fimea.fi/web/en/medical-devices/legislation-related-to-medical-devices</p> <p>National legislation related to national emergency supply https://www.huoltovarmuuskeskus.fi/en/organisation/funding-and-legislation/legislation</p> <p>Comprehensive security operating model https://turvallisuuksomitea.fi/en/comprehensive-security/</p> <p>Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02017R0745-20230320&qid=1691394683480</p> <p>Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in vitro diagnostic medical devices and repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02017R0746-20230320&qid=1691394779377</p>
GERMANY	There are several laws and regulations relating to medical countermeasures. These include the Medicinal Products Act and the Infection Protection Act as well as national regulations implementing European requirements.
ICELAND	<p>Regulation No 817/2012 (under Act No 97/1997), Act No 100/2020 (Medicines) Act No 132/2020 (Medical devices) Regulation No 817/2012 (under Act No 97/1997) PPEs</p> <p>Amendments for Acts on Medicines and Medical Devices pending before Parliament; new Act on Health Security and Communicable Diseases</p>

	pending before Parliament (however legal framework in current health security act legislation is sufficient).
LITHUANIA	Lietuvos Respublikos valstybės rezervo įstatymas (The Law of the State reserve) There are several regulations as well relating to medical countermeasures.
SWEDEN	We do not answer questions about MCM in detail. But there is contingency responsibility at different levels and it is all governed by Swedish legislation – several different legislations.

Important dimensions regarding the MCM-related legal framework emerge in the observations of some EU-HIP partners, including that the MCM legal framework is extensive, involving several laws and regulations. Moreover, it is strongly connected to the legal framework for PHPP and AMR and to the roles of several actors.

The impact of EU-level regulations must also be considered – particularly with regard to the mandate of the EMA mandate and the International Health Regulations revision.

3.4.3 Key actors and stakeholders' network

The table in Annex 5 provides an overview of the main stakeholders per country concerning MCM. The various stakeholders concerning MCM and their respective roles in different consortium member countries can be summarized as follows:

- **Ministries of Health** with responsibility for policy making, coordination of health response to severe threats and incidents, monitoring and coordinating the state of MCM preparedness
- **Medicines agencies** with responsibility to ensure the quality, safety, and efficacy of medicines, health products and medical devices; monitoring medicine shortages; supply reliability and preparedness for pharmaceutical products; and authorization of wholesale permits to commercial and public organizations.
- **Emergency supply agencies** that manage the stockpiling of all essential resources including strategic pharmaceutical stock.
- **Public Health Institutions** have responsibilities for stockpiles; maintaining national health care registers for primary and secondary care; and disease control.
- **Social insurance institutions** gather data related to the usage and costs of medicines and maintain the national patient archive.
- **Other specialized agencies and health care providers** might i.a. provide an infrastructure to produce and distribute vaccines and therapeutics as quickly as possible in the event of a pandemic; guarantee and regulate the activity of transfusion medicine and transplantation.

4 Preparing the ground for EU-HIP sustainability

Deliverable D4.1 – Landscape analysis report summarizes the findings of a successful activity to map, analyze and compare digital infrastructures and systems (including, when possible, data and their standards), key actor and stakeholder networks, as well as pertinent legislative aspects in the EU-HIP countries, in order to identify best practices and lessons learned. The findings of this analysis will provide the project with key reference points for building towards sustainability.

In order to construe the results in a suitable sustainability framework we have reviewed the relevant results of other thematically aligned projects such as PHIRI, TEHDAS and SHARP JAs and extracted components applicable to the sustainability work of EU-HIP. We adapted, for example the basic structure of the country visit methodology used in PHIRI and TEHDAS to the specific needs of EU-HIP and we mapped the sustainability dimensions proposed by prior data collection tools to the areas identified by the EU-HIP draft common framework developed by WP5. Moreover, EU-HIP benefits from reviewing the main findings and lessons learned from prior projects, by utilizing them as a means of focusing on identified areas of either best practices or clear development gaps.

The work that EU-HIP and the HERA platform ATHINA intend to support is one closely connected to the main targets of the Health Union, as well as national public health systems – preparing and protecting the population from cross-border health threats. This is an area where the benefits of health data reuse have already been demonstrated during the covid-19 pandemic. The EU environment of health data reuse will be shaped in the coming years through the implementation of the EHDS Regulation, with interoperability as one of its cornerstones.

Taking into account the EU-HIP project's main objective of interoperability promotion and facilitation, the scope of our sustainability activities and focus of WP4 forthcoming work can be outlined as follows:

- Promoting synergies between the EHDS *activities for protection against serious cross-border threats to health, and public health surveillance or activities ensuring high levels of quality and safety of healthcare* and EU-HIP activities;
- Fostering a cooperative governance of data sharing for surveillance and monitoring of health threats;
- Understanding and demonstrating how EU-HIP sustainability outcomes could be useful for the EHDS ecosystem.

5 References

1. International Health Regulations, https://www.who.int/health-topics/international-health-regulations#tab=tab_1
2. The European Commission's Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA), https://health.ec.europa.eu/health-emergency-preparedness-and-response-hera_en
3. “HERA IT System ‘ATHINA’ to collect intelligence and assess threats: call for tender published”, https://health.ec.europa.eu/latest-updates/hera-it-system-athina-collect-intelligence-and-assess-threats-call-tender-published-2023-04-25_en
4. Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space – TEHDAS, <https://tehdas.eu/>
5. PHIRI – the Population Health Information Research Infrastructure project, <https://www.phiri.eu/>
6. Joint External Evaluations <https://www.who.int/emergencies/operations/international-health-regulations-monitoring-evaluation-framework/joint-external-evaluations>
7. Joint External Evaluation Tool, <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240051980>
8. WHO, Support tool to strengthen health information systems: guidance for health information system assessment and strategy development. Available at: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/342126>
9. TEHDAS WP4 – Outreach, engagement and sustainability. Overview of results, https://tehdas.eu/results/?_package=wp-4-outreach-engagement-and-sustainability
10. PHIRI WP3 - Outreach, engagement and sustainability. <https://www.phiri.eu/wp3>
11. PHIRI WP3 One pager-reports, <https://www.phiri.eu/one-pagers>
12. Information for Action Joint Action – InfAct. <https://www.inf-act.eu/>
13. TEHDAS WP4 – Country visit Fact Sheets: <https://tehdas.eu/packages/package-4-outreach-engagement-and-sustainability/tehdas-country-visits/>

6 Annexes

Annex 1: EU-HIP Landscape mapping tool

Separate Excel-file.

Annex 2: AMR supplementary materials

When examining the actual AMR related findings, it is important to observe the completion rate of the survey questions upon which these findings are based.

In order to estimate the representativeness and coverage achieved in the EU-HIP questionnaire data collection process, we calculated the degree of response completeness for each country of the 15 EU-HIP Consortium members for the three questionnaire domains covered in the AMR topic: Digital infrastructures and systems, Key actors and stakeholders' network and Legislative aspects

- **In-full** indicates that the country has answered all questions in the AMR section;
- **Partial** indicates that the country has answered part of the questions in the section;
- **Not available*** indicates that the country did not respond to any of the questions in the sub-section.

* refers to a section (or individual questions) left blank. This category does not include No answers: these are considered answers provided in all respects.

As demonstrated in Figure 1, the data taken into consideration for the analysis of AMR include a strong (62.2%) “In-full” completion which, combined with Partial (28.9%), corresponds to a total of 91.1% of survey responses collected.

Figure 1: Overall completion rate of the AMR domain

The domain that records the highest number of **Partial** responses is the one concerning *Digital infrastructures*, which describes the state of the art of digital health surveillance data systems applied to sectors such as the detection, collection, and identification of information at country level.

Figure 2: Percentage of Partial responses in the AMR domain

As can be seen from Figure 3 below, the sub-sections *Legislative aspects* (identification of the regulations and agreements governing the exchange of health surveillance data within the country system and with external stakeholders/organizations) and *Key actors and stakeholders' network* (identification of the actors involved in health surveillance data exchange systems) recorded an even number of blank information fields.

Figure 3: Percentage of Not available responses in the AMR domain

Table 1: Examples of pertinent key actors and stakeholders in the AMR domain

Country	Examples of key actors and stakeholders
Belgium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> For surveillance: Sciensano, a research institute and national public institute. It is a federal institution operating under the authority of the federal minister of Public Health and the federal minister of Agriculture For all the topics related to human health: The Belgian Antibiotic Policy Coordination Committee (BAPCOC), with its several working groups (outpatient medicine, hospital

	<p>medicine, platforms for hospital hygiene, awareness, outpatient medicine, hospital medicine, awareness, veterinary medicine)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the definition of the conditions for reimbursement of drugs, collecting data on antibiotic prescriptions and for the drafting of reports on antibiotic feedback: The Centre of Expertise on Antimicrobial Resistance and Antimicrobial Consumption in Animals in Belgium (AMCRA); The Multidrug Resistant Organisms (MDRO) Task Force; The Antibiotic Convention in Veterinary Medicine; The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance; The Communities and Regions; the Federal Agency of Medicines and Health Products
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdisciplinary section for antibiotic resistance control (ISKRA) of the Croatian Ministry of Health and Social Welfare. • Croatian Institute of Public Health • Clinic for Infectious Diseases “dr. Fran Mihaljević”
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the political oversight and interministerial coordination: The Ministry of the Interior and Health. • For health preparedness planning, guidelines, notification regulations, coordination of response across health sector and agencies, public health guidance for the public: Danish Health Authority. • For surveillance reference diagnostics, expert guidance, risk assessment, public health guidance, guidelines for health professionals: Statens Serum Institut. • For contact tracing, local public health measures and guidance: Danish Patient Safety Authority. • For regulation, safety protocols, supply, and accessibility: Danish Medical Agency. • For hospital management: Regional Authorities. • For primary care services and municipal preparedness planning: Municipal Authorities.
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • THL coordinates the FiRe network FiRe consists of all 21 Finnish clinical microbiology laboratories and the Bacteriology Team of the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare. The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare coordinates the FiRe network and provides both technical and specialist support. The institute maintains and develops the Finres antimicrobial susceptibility database. Surveillance of antimicrobial resistance - THL
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For analysis of alert reports and provision of expert advice: Support center for the prevention of healthcare-associated infections (CPias), contributing to the development and application of the national and regional strategy for the prevention of infections associated with care and the control of resistance to anti-infectives • For implementation of management measures and connection with the central authority: Regional Health Agencies (ARS), responsible for regional management of the national health system • For provision of second-line support to the CPias and responsible for national alerts (in conjunction with the French Ministry of Health or other Health Agencies): Public Health National Agency
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Robert Koch Institute (RKI) is a German federal government agency and research institute responsible for disease control and prevention. • The Federal Health Authorities • The Local Health Departments
Iceland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist (Centre for Health Security and Communicable Disease Control at the Directorate of Health) • The Directorate of Health • The Icelandic Food and Veterinary Authority • The National Reference Lab at Landspítali - National University Hospital • Landspítali - National University Hospital • The Primary Care Service • The Primary Care Development Center (ÞÍH) • The Association of Welfare Services (SFV) • The Ministry of Health • The Icelandic Medicines Agency • The University of Iceland - Keldur
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National plan to combat antibiotic resistance (PNCAR) and preparation and drafting of the PNCAR: Ministry of Health and competent Ministries.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of information, quality control of data sent by laboratories, analysis and dissemination of data: National Health Institute (ISS) - Department of Infectious Diseases. • Extraction of antibiotic resistance data: Microbiology laboratories. • Identification of the participating laboratories making the data of the regional surveillance network available: Regions
Lithuania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Health • The National public health surveillance laboratory • National Public Health Centre under the Ministry of Health • The health care institutions
Netherlands	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For local and regional surveillance and response: The public health services, and regional AMR care networks • For local institutional infection prevention and control: IPC-professionals and clinicians (laboratories, hospitals, nursing homes, GP) • For national surveillance and response: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment • Many stakeholders, including the Dutch Working Party on Antibiotic Policy (Dutch acronym is SWAB), Wageningen Food Safety Research (WFSR), e Food and Consumer Product Safety Authority, Netherlands Veterinary Medicines Institute, National Influenza Center, Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research (Nivel) • Ministry of Health
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Norwegian institute of public health • Municipality/public health /hospital medical doctor • Medical laboratories/ reference laboratories/ NORM-surveillance network • Ministry of Health / Directorate of Health. • Stakeholders within one-health sector
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination of the health priority programme for AMR (PPCIRA): the Directorate-General of Health. The PPCIRA governance is based on a three-level structure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Central through Directorate-General of Health ○ Regional, through the PPCIRA Regional Units, which are part of the organization of each Regional Health Administration and which report to the national directorate of the Program ○ Local, through the Local Units of the Program, integrated into the services providing health care of the National Health Service (SNS), namely the groups of health centers (ACES), hospital establishments, local health units (ULS) and inpatient units of the national integrated continued care network (RNCCI)
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Health • National Institute of Public Health • National Reference Laboratory and all public and private laboratories that are dealing with pathogens with high pandemic potential • Infectious diseases hospitals and hospitals that have infectious diseases wards • All Public Health Authorities involved in surveillance • Stakeholders within one-health sector
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the surveillance, data collection, reporting to different stakeholders: The Ministry of Health; the National Antimicrobial Stewardship Committee; the National Committee for the Prevention and Control of Hospital-Acquired Infections (NAKOBO); the National Institute of Public Health • For the diagnosing and reporting: Microbiological laboratories • For risk assessment and risk management: hospitals with their Committee for the Prevention and Control of Hospital-Acquired Infections

Annex 3: PHPP supplementary materials

In order to estimate the representativeness and coverage achieved in the EU-HIP questionnaire data collection process, we calculated the degree of response completeness for each country of the 15 EU-HIP Consortium members for the three questionnaire domains covered in the PHPP topic: Digital infrastructures and systems, Key actors and stakeholders' network and Legislative aspects.

With the aim of placing in context the analysis and reporting of the PHPP section data, we present here at an aggregate level the degree of completion of the respective questionnaire module (Figure 1).

- **In-full** indicates that the country has answered all questions in the module;
- **Partial** indicates that the country has answered part of the questions in the module;
- **Not Available**¹⁸ indicates that the country did not respond to any of the questions in the module.

Figure 4: Overall completion rate of the PHPP module in the EU-HIP questionnaire

The domain which records the highest number of **Partial** responses is the one called *Digital infrastructures and systems*, which describes the state of the art of digital health surveillance data systems applied to sectors such as the detection, collection, and identification of information at country level (Figure 5).

¹⁸ refers to a domain (or individual questions) left blank. This category does not include “No” answers as these are considered as answers provided in all domains' assessments.

Figure 5: Percentage of “Partial” responses in the PHPP domain

Table 2: Examples of pertinent key actors and stakeholders in the PHPP domain

Country	Stakeholders
Belgium	<p>COVID-19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sciensano is responsible for the coordination of output on a national level. • Laboratories are responsible for the collection of information on positive and negative lab tests. • Hospitals collect information on hospitalisations for and with COVID-19. • Regional health authorities are responsible for vaccine roll-out and owner of COVID-19 vaccination data. • UZLeuven is genomic surveillance. <p>Influenza viruses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sciensano is responsible for the surveillance (Epidemiological services involved: Epidemiology of infectious diseases, Health service research, Healthcare-associated infections and antimicrobial resistance / Viral service: NRC-I) and vaccine effectiveness control (Laboratoire officiel de contrôle des médicaments (OMCL)). Within Sciensano Healthdata hosts the supporting system for NRC-I and the SARI surveillance. • Communities and regions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Novel influenza: List of mandatory notification diseases (but associated with specific rules: high severity, epidemic potential, absence of therapeutic or when the diagnostic is confirmed) ○ Organisation of the vaccination campaign for seasonal vaccination • FPS Public Health is responsible for communication in the framework of serious cross-border threats to health. • The Belgian Health Care Knowledge Centre (KCE) organises the vaccination campaign and recommendations on vaccination strategy. <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sciensano: surveillance of infectious diseases; epidemic intelligence; coordination of the Risk Assessment Group • Regional health authorities: mandatory notification system (reception of notifications, case investigation, contact tracing and measures) • Federal health authority: crisis preparedness <p>Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerp is the laboratory of reference for detection and identification • The Universitair Ziekenhuis Antwerpen is the reference hospital for FHV • FOD/SPF Public Health: Coordination of the Risk Management Group, EWRS.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional health authorities: Entities to contact in case of declaration or suspicion of cases for risk assessment and contact-tracing and follow-up, participation in the Risk Management Group (RMG) and Risk Assessment Group (RAG). • Sciensano: Surveillance, coordination of the Risk Assessment Group (RAG), TESSy. • Experts in FHV: Risk Assessment Group (RAG) members <p>Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sciensano: surveillance of respiratory viruses (possible support on the request of regional health authorities) • Communities and regions: Entities to contact in case of declaration or suspicion of a respiratory syndrome (acute or severe) in an epidemiological context of a new virus emergence (MERS, new variant of Influenza, SARS) • Universitair Ziekenhuis Antwerpen and UZ Leuven/KU Leuven: National Reference Centre for Respiratory pathogens (except. of Influenza) - (MERS-CoV only Leuven) • FPS Public Health: Communication in the framework of serious cross-border threats to health <p>Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerp : National laboratory of reference for identification • Sciensano : responsible for describing the epidemiology, trends in cases, and identifying risk factors. Surveillance of vectors at a national level • Communities and regions: Entities to contact in case of declaration or suspicion of cases"
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Croatian Institute of Public Health (CIPH) is the leading public health institution in the Republic of Croatia and counties, founded in 1893. The institute conducts activities in the fields of disease epidemiology, public health promotion, prevention, education and environmental health. CIPH has the central role of coordination of the network of the 21 county public health departments (one per county and one for the capital city, Zagreb, which is CIPH). Each county public health department is connected to CIPH and is obliged to report health data. CIPH holds the Croatian National Reference Laboratory for the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (ECDC), the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Reference Centre of the Republic of Croatia for the Ministry of Health. • The Ministry of Health (Ministarstvo zdravstva) is the primary government body responsible for health policy and regulation and it plays a central role in coordinating efforts related to pathogens with high pandemic potential. It formulates strategies, implements regulations and collaborates with other stakeholders to enhance preparedness. • Croatia has also regional public health institutes known as "Zavod za javno zdravstvo" that work in collaboration with CIPH. The role of these regional institutes is to address public health issues at the local and regional levels, providing services and implementing health programs tailored to the specific needs of their respective areas. They support disease surveillance, health promotion, prevention programs and responding to public health emergencies within their designated regions. • The University Hospital for Infectious Diseases (UHID) is the leading institution for diagnostics and treatment of infectious disease in Croatia and the surrounding region. As a leading institution for infectious diseases in Croatia, founded in 1893, UHID also serves as the national reference center for the following areas of expertise: diagnostics and treatment of infectious diseases, viral hepatitis, HIV-infection, urinary tract infections, antibiotic resistance surveillance, tropical and travel medicine and extracorporeal membrane oxygenation (ECMO) in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS).
Denmark	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Interior and Health is responsible for the political oversight, legislation, finance, declaration of health emergency, interministerial coordination • The Danish Health Authority provides guidance for health preparedness planning, guidelines, notification regulations, coordination of response across health sector and agencies and public health guidance for the public • The Statens Serum Institut is responsible for surveillance, reference diagnostics, expert guidance, risk assessment

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Danish Patient Safety Authority is responsible for contact tracing, local public health measures and guidance • Regional authorities (5 regions): hospital, emergency and general practice services, regional preparedness planning, vaccination services • Municipal authorities (98 municipalities): primary care services, municipal preparedness planning
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) is a governmental research and development institute under the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health. Its responsibilities include monitoring public health, preventing diseases, and providing evidence-based information for health policy decision-making. • The Finnish Food Authority is primarily responsible for ensuring the safety and quality of food and animal feed in Finland. In the context of pathogens, it may be involved in monitoring and surveilling foodborne illnesses. The authority may collaborate with other agencies to investigate and manage outbreaks related to contaminated food. • The Ministry of Social Affairs and Health plays a central role in setting health policy in Finland and for implementing public health measures in response to emerging infectious diseases. • Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Finland; Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry; Ministry of the Environment; Ministry of Employment and the Economy; Ministry of the Interior • Finnish Medicines Agency (Fimea) is responsible for regulating medicinal products in Finland. • The Centre for Biothreat Preparedness (BUOS) is a national specialist organisation for the management of biosecurity medicine and biological threats. It aims to support the fight against biological threats caused by the deliberate spread of microorganisms. It also supports preparedness for threats and increases knowledge and cooperation in the field at the national level. The Centre for Biothreat Preparedness is a joint project of the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, the Finnish Defence Forces and the Finnish Food Authority. It is directed by a steering group consisting of members from the institutes and the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, the Ministry of Defence, and the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. • Municipalities and the Regional State Administrative Agencies play a role in implementing and coordinating local responses to infectious diseases, including surveillance and control measures.
France	<p>Roles and responsibilities at national level regarding infectious disease:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The management of health security policy and organization is ensured by the General Health Directorate from the French Ministry of Health. Within the Sub-Directorate for Health Surveillance and Safety, the Public Health Emergency and Operations Centre (PHEOC - CORRUSS) is ensuring a permanent operational monitoring (24 hours a day) of national and international health events or alerts, as well as any information coming from other regions, territories or ministries. • Infectious disease surveillance relies on numerous partners and stakeholders who form a national public health network in which clinicians and biologists are on the front line. The French surveillance system for infectious diseases is based on mandatory reporting, national reference centers, networks of voluntary professionals and repeated surveys. These systems are coordinated by the Santé Publique France, whose mission is to monitor the state of health of the population, to alert public authorities to public health threats, and to study the determinants of changes in health trends. health status. <p>Roles and responsibilities at regional level regarding infectious disease:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In each ARS, a regional monitoring and health emergency platform receives and analyses all reports of events likely to threaten the health of the population or cause a media or even political crisis. This platform brings together the Inter-Regional Epidemiology Cells (Regional cells of Sante Publique France), responsible for the investigation and evaluation of signals in connection with Sante Publique France, and the monitoring, alert and health management cells (CVAGS) responsible for coordinating the management measures implemented, benefiting from the technical support of the national PHEOC (CORRUSS) if necessary.
Germany	COVID-19

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Health (Bundesministerium für Gesundheit - BMG) was responsible for the coordination of the national strategy, formulating guidelines, and communicating public health measures. It collaborated with various federal and state entities to ensure a unified and effective approach to managing the pandemic. • As Germany's national public health institute, the Robert Koch Institute (RKI) is responsible for monitoring and analysing the COVID-19 data. It provided scientific guidance to policymakers, issued testing and contact tracing protocols, and disseminated epidemiological data to inform decision-making at both federal and local levels. • The Federal Health Authorities (Gesundheitsämter), including local health departments, operated at the regional and local levels, implementing public health measures and managing COVID-19 cases. They were responsible for contact tracing, testing, and coordinating isolation and quarantine efforts. • The Local Health Departments (Gesundheitsämter at the regional and local levels) were on the frontline of the COVID-19 response, executing contact tracing, testing, and enforcing isolation and quarantine measures for affected individuals. They worked closely with healthcare providers and other stakeholders to ensure a coordinated and localized approach to addressing the challenges posed by the pandemic within their respective jurisdictions. <p>Other pathogens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Robert Koch Institute • Federal Health Authorities • Local Health Department
Iceland	<p>COVID-19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist (Centre for Health Security and Communicable Disease Control at the Directorate of Health) is responsible for monitoring and analysing the spread of the virus, provide expert guidance to the government, formulate evidence-based recommendations and communicate information to the public. • The Ministry of Health formulated and implemented national health policies during the COVID-19 pandemic. It coordinated resources, provided guidelines for testing, contact tracing, and quarantine measures, and ensured that healthcare facilities, including hospitals like Landspítali, were well-prepared to handle COVID-19 cases. • The Landspítali (National University Hospital including the Reference Lab) supported testing for COVID-19, diagnosing cases and providing medical care for individuals with severe symptoms. The hospital's Reference Lab played a significant role in processing and analyzing COVID-19 tests, contributing to Iceland's overall testing strategy and response to the pandemic. <p>Influenza</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist (Centre for Health Security and Communicable Disease Control at the Directorate of Health) • Ministry of Health • Landspítali - National University Hospital including the Reference Lab <p>Other pathogens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist • The National Reference Lab at Landspítali - National University Hospital
Italy	<p>In this sequence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General practitioners: first point of contact for individuals with symptoms, conducting initial assessments, providing medical advice and referring patients for testing or hospitalization when necessary. • The Italian Armed Forces Health Corps (USMAF) were responsible for setting up field hospitals, providing medical assistance, transporting patients and collaborating with civilian healthcare institutions. The USMAF contributed valuable resources and expertise to reinforce the healthcare system during the pandemic. • Local Health Authorities implemented public health measures and managed the response to COVID-19 at the regional and local levels. They were responsible for contact tracing, testing coordination, quarantine measures and ensuring the availability of healthcare

	<p>resources within their jurisdictions. Local health authorities played a key role in adapting national guidelines to the specific needs of their regions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Italy's regional governments (Regions) coordinated with local health authorities, implemented national guidelines and tailored responses to the specific needs of their regions. Regions were responsible for managing healthcare resources, overseeing hospital capacities, and collaborating with national health authorities to ensure a coordinated approach to the pandemic. The Ministry of Health coordinated the national response to COVID-19. It developed and communicated national guidelines, provided support to regional health authorities, and coordinated efforts to secure medical supplies and resources. The Ministry of Health also liaised with international organizations and facilitated collaboration between different stakeholders to ensure a unified approach to managing the pandemic. The Istituto Superiore di Sanità (ISS) provided scientific guidance, conducted surveillance and data analysis, developed national guidelines, coordinated research efforts and played a key role in international collaboration. ISS also communicated information to the public and facilitated training for healthcare professionals.
<p>Lithuania</p>	<p>COVID-19 and influenza</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Lithuanian National Public Health Center (NPHC) conducts epidemiological surveillance, collects and analyses data on the spread of these diseases. NPHC provides scientific guidance, develops guidelines and support coordination of public health threats. The Ministry of Health formulates and implements national health policies, coordinates resources and provides guidelines for testing, contact tracing and treatment. The MoH works closely with various stakeholders, including the NPHC, to adapt strategies and responses to the evolving situations posed by these respiratory illnesses. The National Public Health Surveillance Laboratory (NPHSL) conducted testing for both COVID-19 and influenza, contributing to the identification and confirmation of cases. The NPHSL played a crucial role in providing timely and accurate laboratory data. <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, yellow fever, dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NPHC HESC <p>Zika, Chikungunya</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NPHC MoH
<p>The Netherlands</p>	<p>COVID-19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) played a central role in coordinating the response to COVID-19 in the Netherlands. They provided information, guidance and recommendations to healthcare professionals, policymakers and the public. The Netherlands Institute for Health Services Research (Nivel) is responsible for collecting data from primary care settings, including information on COVID-19 incidence and trends. This data helps in monitoring the spread of the virus and informing public health decision. Medical laboratories Hospitals <p>Influenza viruses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The National Influenza Centre (NIC) - Erasmus MC is responsible for antigenic characterizations of influenza viruses, which is crucial for vaccine strain selection and monitoring virus evolution. The National Influenza Center is a collaboration between the RIVM and the Erasmus Medical Center (Erasmus MC). A large number of hospital laboratories in the Netherlands send samples in which the flu virus has been found to the RIVM or the Erasmus MC. This determines which type of flu virus it is and what properties it has. This is necessary to determine whether the vaccines also match the viruses that are circulating.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar to its role in COVID-19 surveillance, Nivel collects data on influenza-like illness (ILI) incidence from primary care settings, contributing to influenza monitoring and research. • Medical laboratories <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical laboratories • Municipal health services
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Norwegian institute of public health (NIPH) is responsible for surveillance of various parameters related to COVID-19 as well as provide MCMs (vaccines). • Municipality/public health medical doctor
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Health's mission is to create, drive, implement, and review national health policy, managing the national health service, guaranteeing the sustainable application and use of resources, and assessing their outcomes. • The Directorate-General for Health (DGS) has the mission of regulating, guiding and coordinating health promotion and disease prevention activities, defining the technical conditions for the adequate provision of health care, planning and programming national policy for quality in the health system, as well as ensuring the preparation and execution of the National Health Plan (PNS). • The Health System Administration (ACSS) is a public organization dedicated to managing the human, financial and infrastructure resources of the Ministry of Health and the National Health System (NHS). Its main responsibilities include planning and coordinating the NHS's financial resources, developing policies for healthcare professionals, establishing financing models for healthcare services and coordinating healthcare facilities and equipment. ACSS also consolidates statistical information, promotes shared resource management, and serves as a national point of contact for cross-border healthcare. ACSS also provides, with some providers, financing for the acquisition of MCM, as an example the execution of seasonal vaccination programs. However, it is important to note that monitoring the execution of this funding is not the role of the ACSS. • The Doctor Ricardo Jorge National Health Institute (INSA) is a public body integrated into the indirect administration of the State, under the supervision of the Ministry of Health, with scientific, technical, administrative, financial autonomy and its own assets. As a State Laboratory, the Ricardo Jorge Institute's mission is to contribute to gains in public health through research and technological development activities, reference laboratory activity, health observation and epidemiological surveillance, as well as coordinating the external assessment of laboratory quality, disseminating scientific culture, promote training and training and also ensure the provision of differentiated services in the aforementioned areas. • Serviços Partilhados do Ministério da Saúde (SPMS)'s mission is to provide specific shared services in the area of health in terms of purchasing and logistics, financial services, human resources, information and communication systems and technologies and other complementary and subsidiary activities, to all establishments and NHS services. SPMS is responsible for the management of the technical and human resources that are necessary for the adequate development and functioning of SINAVE, the National Epidemiological Surveillance System. Besides that, SPMS guarantees the existence of a contact channel with users to provide any clarifications requested and to allow the resolution of problems that may arise when using the computer application support for SINAVE. • The National Authority for Medicines and Health Products, I. P. (INFARMED, I.P.) is a public institute with a special regime, under the terms of the law, integrated into the indirect administration of the State, endowed with administrative, financial autonomy and its own assets. Infarmed's mission is to regulate and supervise the sectors of medicines for human use and health products, according to the highest standards of public health protection, and to guarantee access for health professionals and citizens to quality medicines and health products, effective and safe. INFARMED is not part of EU-HIP consortium. For that reason, information on MCMs may not be completed.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Regional Health Administrations, I. P. (ARS, I. P.) have the mission of ensuring regional planning of resources, from a perspective of intersectoral coordination, promoting territorial cohesion in the area of health and developing activities within the scope of public health and behaviour additives and dependencies. • The Portuguese Environment Agency, I. P. (APA, I. P.) has the mission of proposing, developing and monitoring the integrated and participatory management of environmental and sustainable development policies, in conjunction with other sectoral policies and in collaboration with public and private entities that compete for the same purpose, having with a view to a high level of protection and enhancement of the environment and the provision of high-quality services to citizens. • The mission of the Portuguese Blood and Transplant Institute (IPST, IP) is to guarantee and regulate the activity of transfusion medicine and transplantation at national level and to guarantee the donation, collection, analysis, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human blood, blood components, organs, tissues and cells of human origin. • The National Public Health Council (CNSP) is established by the government member in charge of the health area in which they are seated, and they have the authority to assign powers to the Director-General of Health. The Council is made up of up to 20 members who are chosen to represent the public, private, and social sectors, as well as academic and scientific fields. The Council serves as an advisory body to the government regarding the prevention and control of communicable diseases and other risks to public health, particularly with regard to the assessment and analysis of serious situations like large-scale epidemic outbreaks and pandemics. The Council is also tasked with justifying a proposal to declare a state of emergency because of a public disaster. • The Clinical Terminology Center's mission is to harmonize and orchestrate the use of clinical terminologies for recording information in National Health Service institutions and to support the introduction of good practices, which lead to the consolidation of meaning and increased usefulness of recorded information, by health professionals. SPMS acquired a license to use SNOMED CT in the national territory, since January 2014. This license allows its free distribution and use in Portugal. • Healthcare providers are also an important actor in this field, since they are the ones primarily identifying and notifying different sources of diseases. Same principle applies to the laboratories that must notify the mandatory communicable diseases to the national authorities as explained above. <p>COVID-19</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS, INSA. DGS is responsible for: risk assessment and risk management, information and documentation relevant to COVID-19, regarding vaccination, recommendations on respiratory infections, declarations and certificates, testing and isolation. It also provides the status of vaccination and epidemiological situation monitoring reports. <p>Influenza</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS, INSA. DGS is responsible for providing relevant information and documentation, FAQs, standards, guidelines, communications and orders issued, and dissemination of information materials. <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management. <p>Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management, providing relevant information and documentation, FAQs, standards, guidelines, communications and orders issued, and dissemination of information materials. <p>Lassa fever</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management. <p>Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS, INSA. DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management. <p>Rift Valley fever DGS and Directorate-General for Food and Veterinary (DGAV)</p>
--	---

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management for human health. DGAV is responsible for animal health. <p>Zika, Chikungunya, yellow fever, dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGS, INSA.DGS is responsible for risk assessment and risk management, providing relevant information and documentation, FAQs, standards, guidelines, communications and orders issued, and dissemination of information materials.
Romania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> COVID-19 and influenza Ministry of Health (Ministerul Sănătății) is responsible for the shaping and executing of national health policies. With a focus on public health, the ministry coordinates strategies for disease surveillance and control. It allocates resources and provides guidance to institutions like the National Institute of Public Health - National Center for Communicable Disease Surveillance and Control (NIPH-NCCDSC) to ensure a unified and effective response to health challenges. NIPH-NCCDSC: as part of the Ministry of Health, specializes in the surveillance and control of communicable diseases in Romania. This institution plays a vital role in monitoring infectious diseases, conducting research, and coordinating responses to outbreaks. <p>Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are no domestic cases, only imports; no dedicated surveillance system
Slovenia	<p>COVID-19, Crimean-Cong haemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary care and hospitals The microbiological laboratories are responsible for diagnosing and reporting infectious diseases. They conduct tests, analyse samples and provide data for the surveillance and monitoring of pathogens. The Ministry of Health (MoH) is responsible for formulating and implementing national health policies, including those related to infectious disease surveillance. It plays a central role in coordinating resources, providing guidelines, and ensuring that the healthcare system is well-prepared to respond to health challenges. The MoH collaborates with various stakeholders, including primary care, hospitals, and laboratories, to create a cohesive and effective national response. The National Institute of Public Health (NIPH) conducts public health research, surveillance and expertise. It plays a vital role in monitoring and controlling infectious diseases, preparedness and response plans, collecting data, risk assessments, risk management, providing data and advising the Ministry of Health on public health policies. The NIPH collaborates with healthcare providers, laboratories, and other stakeholders to ensure a comprehensive and evidence-based approach to disease surveillance and response. <p>Influenza</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primary care and hospitals microbiological laboratories MoH NIPH Administration for Food Safety, Veterinary Sector and Plant Protection is involved in surveillance to monitor influenza activity in animal, implementing preventive measures such as biosecurity protocols and vaccination programs, and coordinating responses to outbreaks that pose a risk to human health. Their efforts include assessing the potential risk of transmission from animals to humans and providing recommendations and reports to mitigate these risks.
Sweden	<p>The Public Health Agency of Sweden (Folkhälsomyndigheten, PHAS) is responsible for public health surveillance, including the monitoring and control of infectious diseases such as COVID-19. It provides expert guidance, conducts risk assessments and formulates public health strategies. The agency supported the coordination of the national response to the</p>

	<p>pandemic, offering recommendations to the government and disseminating information to the public.</p> <p>Crimean-Cong haemorrhagic fever, Ebola virus disease and Marburg virus disease, Lassa fever, Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS), Rift Valley fever, Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Regions • PHAS and Academia • The Swedish Medicines Agency oversees the regulation and safety of medicines, including those related to pathogen surveillance. It focuses on ensuring that pharmaceutical products used in the detection, prevention, and treatment of infectious diseases meet safety and efficacy standards. The agency's involvement in pathogen surveillance extends to monitoring and regulating antiviral medications, vaccines and other pharmaceuticals.
--	--

Table 3: Main legislations relevant to pathogens with high pandemic potential and pandemic preparedness plans

Country	Main legislations	Pandemic preparedness plan(s)
Belgium	<p>Memorandum of understanding between Belgian health authorities regarding public health threats and cross-border threats in the application of the International Health Regulation</p>	<p>Belgian Health Emergency Plan, published in January 2023</p> <p>Pandemic preparedness plan for Ebola, Marburg and Lassa fever virus diseases</p> <p>The Federal Public Service is currently updating pandemic preparedness plans for influenza, MERS and SARS</p>
Croatia	<p>Law on the Protection of the Population from Infectious Diseases establishes which infectious diseases are subject to prevention and control, as well as measures to protect the population. The law also provides for security and emergency measures, system of monitoring and control, and offences and penalties.</p> <p>During the COVID-19 pandemic, the Government of the Republic of Croatia passed the Disaster Risk Assessment for the Republic of Croatia, based on the Article 10 – Paragraph 1 of the Civil Protection System Act. From this application a long-term Disaster Risk Management Strategy (until 2030), was created.</p> <p>Croatian Act on Data and Information in the Health Care System (2019): regulates processing of data in the healthcare system in compliance with GDPR</p>	<p>National Recovery and Resilience Plan 2021 - 2026 is in place, containing a part regarding strengthening the resilience in case of future pandemics.</p>
Denmark	<p>Health Act (Sundhedsloven)</p> <p>Epidemics Act (Epidemiloven)</p>	<p>National strategy for pandemic preparedness (2013) focusing on influenza: published by Danish Health Authority. Strategy is under revision and will be made more generic.</p>

	<p>Executive Order on health preparedness planning (Bekendtgørelse om planlægning af sundhedsberedskabet)</p>	<p>Each region and each agency has its own preparedness plan. Regions and municipalities must, among other scenarios, plan for management of communicable diseases in general.</p> <p>General coordinating plans for civil preparedness, including for pandemics/epidemics at the national level.</p>
Finland	<p>Communicable diseases Act (1986) and Government Decree on Communicable diseases (2016): in process of update 2023-2027</p> <p>Government Decree on protecting workers from risks arising from biological agents</p> <p>Decree of the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health on the classification of biological agents</p> <p>Emergency law- in process of update, draft proposal by end 2024</p>	<p>No pandemic preparedness plan reported</p>
France	<p>Law No. 78-17 of January 6, 1978 relating to data processing, files and freedoms (article 6)</p> <p>Decree No. 2023-700 of July 31, 2023 relating to the compulsory transmission of individual data to the health authority and the creation of the processing of personal data ("LABOé-SI" IT System)</p>	<p>Pandemic preparedness plans in place for COVID-19, influenza, Ebola and Marburg virus diseases, MERS, SARS, Zika and Chikungunya.</p> <p>Pandemic preparedness plans in development for CCHF, Lassa fever and Rift Valley fever.</p>
Germany	<p>Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG) specifies the regulations of the GDPR for Germany and contains special regulations on health data management.</p> <p>Infection Protection Act (IfSG): key law for pandemic preparedness, which contains regulations on the reporting of infectious diseases, quarantine and isolation, compulsory vaccination and other measures to combat epidemics.</p> <p>German Social Code V (SGB V): a core law in German social law, which regulates statutory health insurance (SHI). SGB V has an important role in terms of the use of healthcare data.</p> <p>Health Data Usage Act (GDNG) and Digitization Act (DigiG): aims to implement the national digitization strategy for health and care to increase availability and use of data in healthcare and research</p>	<p>Pandemic preparedness plan for COVID-19, influenza and Ebola. It was noted it requires further development.</p> <p>National Pandemic Plan for Germany (NPP): a collection of instructions for action in the event of a pandemic in Germany. It sets out the framework conditions for the pandemic plans of the federal states and the implementation plans of the municipalities. It is therefore primarily aimed at the responsible authorities at federal, state and local level.</p>

	<p>Administrative Regulation on Infection Protection Co-ordination in Cases of Emergency (2013): Defines the structures for inter-sectoral information, coordination and collaboration in case of emergency, especially with the food and animal health sector.</p>	
Iceland	<p>Act on Health Security and Communicable Diseases No 19/1997 (with later amendments).</p> <p>Related Regulations including Regulation on Notifiable Diseases no. 221/2012 with later amendments, most recently no. 848/2023.</p>	<p>Act No 82/2008 on Civil Protection (with later amendments) regarding preparedness and preparedness plans</p>
Italy	No response	<p>National Strategic Operational Plan for Pandemic Influenza Preparedness and Response (PanFlu) 2021-2030</p>
Lithuania	<p>Law on the Health System, Articles 13(1) and 13(2)</p> <p>Law on the Prevention and Control of Communicable Diseases in Humans, Articles 2, 9 and 22</p>	<p>Law on the Prevention and Control of Communicable Diseases in Humans, Articles 2, 9 and 22</p>
Netherlands	<p>Wet publieke gezondheid (Public health law)</p> <p>Health data: <u>The Implementation act of the GDPR (or: (U)AVG)</u>, <u>The Medical Treatment Contracts Act (or: WGBO)</u>, <u>The Wabvpz, Begz,</u> <u>Wegiz, Wet BIG, Wkkgz and NEN-standards.</u></p>	<p>The Netherlands has pandemic preparedness plans in place (under supervision)</p>
Norway	<p>Act relating to control of communicable diseases (Smittevernloven)</p> <p>Act on Health and Social Preparedness (Helseberedskapsloven)</p> <p>Health Register Act (Helseregisterloven)</p> <p>Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases (MSIS) regulation</p> <p>International Health Regulations (IHR-forskriften): implements the IHR (2005), and EU Decision 1082/2013/EU which regulates the EU's EWRS alert system.</p> <p>Norwegian Public Health Act (Folkehelseloven) : Stipulates that the Norwegian Institute of Public Health shall make information available as a basis for the municipalities' and county authorities' overviews. The information shall be based on statistics from central health registers, as well as other relevant statistics. The Norwegian Institute of Public</p>	<p>Pandemic preparedness plan for COVID-19 and influenza.</p>

	Health shall provide assistance, advice, guidance and information in this connection.	
Portugal	<p>Law no. 81/2009, of August 21: establishes a public health surveillance system, which identifies risk situations, collects, updates, analyses and disseminates data on communicable diseases and other public health risks, as well as preparing contingency plans for emergency situations. In this same law, the National Public Health Council (CNSP) is created.</p> <p>Order no. 11035-A/2016, of September 13: creates the Center for Public Health Emergencies (CESP) within the Directorate-General for Health (DGS)</p> <p>Decree-Law no. 82/2009, of April 2 establishes the legal framework for the designation, competence and functioning of entities exercising the power of health authorities</p> <p>Decree n.º 15385-A/2016, of December 21 defines which notifiable communicable diseases and other public health risks should be covered by the information and communication network established by the national epidemiological surveillance system (SINAVE).</p>	<p>Portugal has specific preparedness plans for different pathogen types:</p> <p>COVID-19: National Plan of Preparation and Response to Disease by new coronavirus (COVID-19)</p> <p>Influenza: National Contingency Plan for Pandemic Flu</p> <p>Ebola virus: National Health Sector Contingency Plan for Ebola Virus Disease</p> <p>CCHF and Lassa fever: in need of revision to be integrated with Ebola plan under the umbrella of haemorrhagic fevers</p> <p>MERS and SARS: in need of revision and update following the COVID-19 pandemic</p> <p>Zika, Chikungunya, Yellow fever, Dengue: National Plan for the Prevention and Control of Vector-borne Diseases</p>
Romania	<p>Governmental Decision no. 657/18.05.2022: the methodology for collecting and reporting data for the surveillance of communicable diseases in the National Communicable Diseases Register</p> <p>National Conception for Response in case of epidemics: the civil protection preparedness and response conceptions in case of epidemics</p>	Pandemic preparedness plan in place for influenza.
Slovenia	Healthcare Databases Act and Communicable Diseases Act provide general legal base for basic data processing scenarios, but not for the entire field.	<p>Preparedness plans exist for influenza, Ebola, Zika.</p> <p>Pandemic preparedness plan in development for COVID-19, Chikungunya and Dengue.</p>
Sweden	<p>Communicable diseases Act (2004:168): The legislation on communicable diseases and future pandemics are subject to inquiry, which is due February 2025.</p> <p>National Legislation (2006:544) stipulates that operational preparedness planning for public</p>	<p>Pandemic preparedness plan exists for COVID-19 and influenza.</p> <p>For diseases that are not autochthonous in Sweden, there is a generic response plan should a case or cases be detected.</p> <p>National Legislation (2006:544) stipulates that operational</p>

	<p>health emergencies is the responsibility of the regions and municipalities.</p> <p>Serious cross-border threats to health Act (2006:1570)</p>	<p>preparedness planning for public health emergencies is the responsibility of the regions and municipalities.</p>
--	---	---

Annex 4. CBRN supplementary materials

The three parts of the questionnaire (*Digital infrastructures and systems*, *Key actors and stakeholders' network* and *Legislative aspects*) which refer to the CBRN topic were taken into consideration for each of the 15 EU-HIP consortium members.

- **In-full** indicates that the country has answered all questions in the CBRN section;
- **Partial** indicates that the country has answered part of the questions in the section;
- **Not available*** indicates that the country did not respond to any of the questions in the sub-section.

* refers to a section (or individual questions) left blank. This category does not include No answers: these are considered answers provided in all respects.

As demonstrated in Figure 6, the data taken into consideration for the analysis of CBRN include an “In-full” completion of 48.9%, which, combined with Partial (35.6%), corresponds to a total of 84.5% of survey responses collected.

Figure 6: Overall completion rate of the CBRN domain

The section that records the highest number of **Partial** responses is the one concerning *Digital infrastructures*, which describes the state of the art of digital health surveillance data systems applied to sectors such as the detection, collection, and identification of information at country level (Figure 11).

Figure 7: Percentage of Partial responses in the CBRN domain

As can be seen from Figure 12 below, out of the “Not available” responses in the three sub-sections, the majority is in the sub-section *Legislative aspects* (identification of the regulations and agreements governing the exchange of health surveillance data within the country system and with external stakeholders/organizations).

Figure 8: Percentage of Not available responses in the CBRN domain

Table 4. Examples of the pertinent key actors and stakeholders in the CBRN domain.

Country	Examples of key actors and stakeholders
Belgium	<p>CBRN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local and federal police: law enforcement, security, assist judicial investigation (discipline 3) • Civil security (local fire brigades and national civil protection): first rescue/relief operations (discipline 1) and logistical support (discipline 4) • Medical assistance services (ambulance services, Mobile Urgency Group-MUG) first medical aid on site (discipline 2) • Hospitals and medical practitioners: remote medical aid (discipline 2) • Army/Defense: assistance to discipline 3 & 4 if needed/possible, mandate for CBRN specialised services (demining, orientation lab, CBRN MUG), General Intelligence and Security Service-ADIV-SGRS, military hospital • National Crisis Center: emergency planning and coordination, host of CBRNe Expertise Center (gathers national CBRN stakeholders), information to citizens (discipline 5) • Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and environment: health emergency planning, emergency medical care coordination, health risks and incidents management • Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain (FAVV-AFSCA): food safety and security (inspection, analysis, regulation) • Local and Federal Prosecuting authorities: judicial investigation • Political authorities (ministers, governors): crisis management • Coordination Unit for Threat Analysis-OCAM-OCAD: terrorism, extremism and radicalisation threat data collection and analysis <p>Chemical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil security: on-site measurements, lead of the evaluation cell in case of chemical risks • Chemical analysis lab of the Defense Laboratories: reference lab analysis (for chemical warfare agents and toxic industrial chemicals) (OPCW designated)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-poison center: emergency toxicological information hotline; management of a large body of scientific documentation on toxic agents; organisation of access to antidotes; toxicovigilance <p>Biological</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sciensano (National Health institute): reference lab analysis, risk assessment, biosafety and epidemiology • Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and environment: lead of the evaluation cell in case of biological risks, pandemic preparedness <p>Radiological & Nuclear</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Agency for Nuclear Control (FANC/AFCN) and its affiliated entities (Belgian Nuclear Research Centre - SCK/CEN, Technical Safety Organization - Bel-V): safety authority responsible for protecting workers, the public and the environment from the risks of ionising radiation (radiological and nuclear safety). Lead of the evaluation cell in case of radiological and nuclear risks.
Croatia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of emergency management system for preparedness and response for a nuclear or radiological emergency is the responsibility of Ministry of the Interior (Mol). implementation of protective actions would be performed by the Civil Protection Commander who is supported by the Civil Protection National Headquarters of the Republic of Croatia. The Headquarters is staffed by representatives of all relevant ministries, governmental bodies and other organizations included in the response. • Radiological emergencies are not considered state-level emergencies, and are handled by the licensee, Mol radiological emergency experts and local authorities. The Ministry of the Interior is the competent authority in the Republic of Croatia in the field of radiological and nuclear safety and security. The expert team of the Mol gives advice on protective actions to the civil protection operational headquarters (national and local) and licensee. In the event of a radiological emergency, the licensee is required to inform Mol immediately. • The EPR system includes the following participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ holders of the approval for activities involving ionizing radiation sources, including holders of the approval for transport of ionizing radiation sources, ○ holders of the approval for performing a nuclear activity, ○ holders of the approval for performing operations involving radioactive waste and disused sources ○ scrap metal operators ○ food and/or water business operators and - feed business operators ○ state administration bodies ○ executive and representative bodies of local and regional self-government units ○ civil protection system operational forces ○ authorized technical services ○ ionizing radiation protection experts ○ authorized experts for nuclear safety and ○ others that can contribute to the implementation of protection measures. • The licensee is also required to make an initial provisional assessment of the emergency and its possible consequences and for carrying out urgent protective measures within the facility. It is not expected that urgent protective actions would need to be taken outside of the facility for operators in Croatia.
Finland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Stakeholders: Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Verifin, Ministry of Interior, Police, Finnish Security and Intelligence Service (SUPO), Finnish Border Guard, Ministry of Defence (PLM), Finnish Defence Forces, Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), Centre of Excellence for Biological Threats (BUOS), Centre of Excellence for Severe Chemical Threats, Poison Information Centre, Wellbeing services counties, Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK), Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment, Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes),

	National Emergency Supply Agency, Finnish Food Authority, Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), Finnish Customs.
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The national network of Biotox-Piratox laboratories is part of the national response to nuclear, radiological, biological, chemical and explosive terrorism (NRBC-E). With a broad scope of intervention, this organized and operational network provides the authorities with an analytical capability that can be called upon as part of the response to suspicious packages or parcels, or in the event of activation of the national crisis management system. The national network of Biotox-Piratox laboratories is made up of laboratories capable of detecting the main agents of biological and chemical threats. Its aim is to provide government authorities with the assessment elements they need to make the right decisions. It conducts biological, chemical or toxicological analyses of samples of human, environmental and/or veterinary origin, required for event management (sample routing, detection and identification) or investigation purposes (confirmation and authentication). The organization and governance of this network is based on four entities, whose composition and missions are defined: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The Interministerial Steering Committee, co-chaired by the General Secretariat for Defense and National Security and the General Directorate for Health ○ The Scientific Advisory Board, which oversees the scientific and technical aspects of the network ○ The coordination unit, responsible for monitoring actions decided by the steering committee ○ The National Advisory Unit (CNC), responsible for operational management of events, including assistance with sampling orientation. • The Institute for Radiological Protection and Nuclear Safety (IRSN) is responsible for providing expertise on radiation protection and nuclear safety. • Monitoring environmental radioactivity is based on two remote monitoring networks with a “sentinel” role, distributed throughout the national territory, with a focus on the environment close to the main nuclear sites and large cities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Téléray for remote monitoring of radioactivity in the air; ○ Hydrotéléray for remote monitoring of river water.
Germany	The Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservative and Nuclear Safety, Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance, RKI, Federal Health Authorities, Local Health Departments.
Iceland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist (Centre for Health Security and Communicable Disease Control at the Directorate of Health) • Directorate of Health • Landspítali – National University Hospital • The Icelandic Food and Veterinary Authority • The Icelandic Radiation Safety Authority • The Icelandic Environment Authority • The Icelandic Meteorological Office • Dept of Civil Protection • University of Iceland – Keldur (laboratory) • Ministries of Health, Justice, Environment, Food and Agriculture
Italy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Control of environmental radioactivity: Ministry of ecological transition • Control of food and drink for human and animal consumption: Ministry of Health • Competent authority for internal and external accidents: ISIN - National Inspectorate for Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection • National alarm point: DCP - Department of Civil Protection • Competent authorities for internal events: ISIN and DCP • Competent authority for the activation of the CBRN Emergency Management Plan: DVVFSPDC - Department of Firefighters, Public Rescue and Civil Defence.
Lithuania	National Crisis Management Centre, Ministry of Interior, Fire and Resceu department, Radiation Protection Centre, MoH, State Nuclear Power Safety Inspectorate, State Border

	Guard Service, State food and veterinary service, Municipalities, Customs of the Republic of Lithuania, NPHSL, MoH, NPHSL, MoH, HESC
Netherlands	RIVM, Food and consumer safety authority (NVWA), Min Health, Min Infrastructure and Water management, Authority for Nuclear Safety and Radiation Protection (ANVS), with RIVM and NVWA being the biggest players in early warning networks.
Norway	<p>All CBRN events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Norwegian national Unit for CBRNE Medicine • Norwegian Defense Research Establishment <p>Chemical events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Justice and Public Security • Other ministries • Cooperation Platform for C and E • Advisory Group • County governors • Municipalities / First responders • Other directorates and entities • Norwegian Institute of Public Health <p>Biological events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Health and Care Services • Other ministries • Preparedness Council for Biological Events • Councillors • County governors • Municipalities • Other entities • Norwegian Institute of Public Health • Norwegian Directorate for Civil Protection <p>Radiological / Nuclear events</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nuclear Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DGS • Portuguese Environment Agency, I.P. (APA, I.P.) • Ministry of Defense in case of intentional release
Romania	Ministry of Internal Affairs
Slovenia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Administration for Civil Protection and Disaster Relief: preparedness and management, preparation and operation of the system for protection from natural and other disasters • Ministry of Defence • Ministry of Health and NIPH- Preparednes and response for biological threats

Annex 5. MCM supplementary materials

As a topic area combining the sensitivity of the pertinent information with the constrained expertise represented in the EU-HIP consortium the MCM module of the data collection tool presented the weakest completion rate, with about one third “In Full”- responses (33.3%) and almost another one third (28%) partial responses, for a total of 63.3% response coverage.

- **In-full** indicates that the country has answered all questions in the MCM section;
- **Partial** indicates that the country has answered part of the questions in the section;
- **Not available*** indicates that the country did not respond to any of the questions in the section.

* refers to a section (or individual questions) left blank. This category does not include No answers, which are counted in all sections as answers provided and thus contribute to the “In-full”-percentage.

Table 5. Examples of the pertinent key actors and stakeholders in the MCM domain.

County	Examples of key actors and stakeholders
Belgium	<p>Medicines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Federal Agency for Medicines and Health Products (FAMHP) ensures the quality, safety, and efficacy of medicines for human and veterinary use, health products (including medical devices and accessories), and raw materials for the preparation and production of medicines. It extends its oversight to all operations involving blood, cells, and tissues, classifying them as health products. Additionally, FAMHP actively monitors medicine shortages through the PharmaStatus application. • The National Institute for Health and Disability Insurance (INAMI/RIZIV) manages health insurance in Belgium and gathers data related to the usage and costs of medicines. • As of May 2022, the Strategic Pharmaceutical Stock Platform (PSPS) has been established. It has members from the Ministry of Defense, FAMHP, the FPS, and other relevant stakeholders. The Minister of Public Health has assigned the PSPS the responsibility of creating a priority list for the formation of the strategic pharmaceutical stock, specifically addressing the potential threats of chemical, biological, and radiological terrorism, as well as pandemic threats. <p>Medical devices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FAMHP manages a database of registered medical devices and oversees the approval process for new devices before their introduction to the market. Both distributors and manufacturers of medical devices are required to register their activities with FAMHP. Additionally, they must inform the National Institute for Sickness and Invalidity Insurance (INAMI) about implantable and long-term invasive medical devices being placed on the market in Belgium. INAMI holds competence over all aspects related to reimbursement. • To enhance the traceability of implantable medical devices, FAMHP has developed the Central Traceability Register (RCT). This system, accessible through the eHealth

	platform, centralizes all information pertaining to implantable or invasive medical devices.
Croatia	Directorate for Commodity Stocks is established under the Ministry of Economy and Sustainable Development and manages the stockpiling of all essential resources, including MCM. That means that data of all stockpiling is stored centrally in this Directorate on national level. Data of stockpiling is classified as confidential / state secret and is not shared with other stakeholders within the country, or such agreements are classified as well and we have no knowledge about them.
Denmark	The Danish Critical Supply Agency (SFOS) https://sfos.dk/english/
Finland	<p>Medicines & medical devices</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Finnish Medicines Agency (FIMEA) ensures, from development to use, the quality, safety and efficacy of medicines for human and veterinary use, pharmacy made and officinal preparations, of health products, including medical devices and accessories, and raw materials for the preparation and production of medicines and of all operations involving blood, cells and tissues, which are also defined as health products. FIMEA maintains a database of registered medical devices and oversees the approval process for new devices before they can be placed on the market. • The Social Insurance institution (Kela) is responsible for managing health insurance in Finland and collects data related to the use and costs of medicines. Kela is responsible for maintaining the national patient archive including ePrescription and eDispensation services. The archive contains information on all medication prescribed and dispensed through pharmacies in Finland but lacks information on medication used in hospital setting. • The Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) is responsible for maintaining national health care registers for primary and secondary care including both the public and private sector. Registries contain information on medication used and prescribed. The delay is upto 7 days in primary care and upto 30 days in secondary care. • The National Emergency Supply Agency (NESA) is responsible for stockpiling emergency supplies including PPE. • THL and NESA are sharedly responsible for operating RescEU stockpile on CBRN threats where THL is responsible for medication and NESA is responsible for supplies. <p>State of MCM preparedness is monitored and coordinated at a national level by the advisory board on states of emergency (PONK) under the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health (MSAH) and its committees on e.g. MCM and material logistics. THL collects data on preparedness and capabilities from the well-being services counties to support the work of the committees and MSAH.</p>
Germany	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices: carry out the risk recording and assessment of drugs and medical devices. • Federal Ministry of Health • Robert Koch-Institute: disease control • Paul-Ehrlich-Institute 's Center for Pandemic Vaccines and Therapeutics (ZEPAI): provide an infrastructure to produce and distribute vaccines and therapeutics as quickly as possible in the event of a pandemic
Iceland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Chief Epidemiologist • The Icelandic Medicines Agency • Landspítali University Hospital • The Ministry of Health
Lithuania	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Health • Health Emergency Situations Centre of the Ministry of Health
Norway	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Norwegian Medical Products Agency (NOMA) (earlier Norwegian Medicines Agency) - does not differentiate between AMR, CBRN or HPPP health threats. Due to major changes in the health sector in Norway and as of 2024 NOMA will take a leading role related to supply reliability and preparedness for pharmaceutical products. • Regional Health Enterprises are also important stakeholders regarding national stocks of PPE and regional competence center for coordination of Medical Technology Development investments.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Health and Care Services (HOD) is responsible for providing good and equal health and care services. Coordination of health response to severe threats and incidences. Policy maker and statutory body. • The Norwegian Directorate of Health (HDIR) is the specialist and authority body under the Ministry of Health and Care.
Portugal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Authority for Medicines and Health Products, I. P. (INFARMED, I.P.) is a public institute with a special regime, under the terms of the law, integrated into the indirect administration of the State, endowed with administrative, financial autonomy and its own assets. Infarmed's mission is to regulate and supervise the sectors of medicines for human use and health products, according to the highest standards of public health protection, and to guarantee access for health professionals and citizens to quality medicines and health products, effective and safe. INFARMED is not part of EU-HIP consortium. For that reason, information on MCMs may not be completed. https://www.infarmed.pt/web/infarmed/apresentacao • The mission of the Portuguese Blood and Transplant Institute (IPST, IP) is to guarantee and regulate the activity of transfusion medicine and transplantation at national level and to guarantee the donation, collection, analysis, processing, preservation, storage and distribution of human blood, blood components, organs, tissues and cells of human origin. Its duties include <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ To coordinate, at national level, the collection, testing, processing and transfusion of blood, as well as the collection, testing, processing and transplantation of organs, tissues and cells of human origin; ○ To ensure the operation of the National Hemovigilance System and the National Biovigilance System, in conjunction with the competent national and international bodies. ○ https://ipst.pt/index.php/pt/institucional/missao-atribuicoes-visao-valores
Sweden	<p>Swedish Medical Products Agency (MPA)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are documents and mechanisms to prevent shortages and supply at the national level. • The MPA has several regulatory tools in place that were practised during e.g. the Covid-19 pandemic. These are e.g. national restriction of prescription to certain prescriber groups if necessary, and different types of exemptions of supplies/demands on both medicinal products and medical devices. Also, if necessary, exemptions to information (labeling) normally required at the national level on medicinal products. • The MPA is also the authority to authorize wholesale permits to commercial and public organisations. • There are collaborative groups at the national level held by the MPA with stakeholders and Health Care for both medicinal products and medical devices, to regularly get first hand information on any risks of shortages (ADL-meetings, Dialogforum-MT). • The MPA has also implemented sanction fees to those commercial suppliers (MAH) that do not report shortages on time (legal framework). SE/the EU has also implemented a “chain of custody of medicinal products” to ensure that medicines delivered to patients fulfil requirements of the legal framework. • There are many government assignments in Sweden ongoing to sharpen tools for horizon scanning, supplies and to mitigate shortages. Also, the European Commission has proposed new legislations, not yet negotiated, to support mitigation of shortages and production on MPs and MDs. As legislation for medicinal products and medical devices is extensively harmonized at the EU level, the MPA takes active part in collaborative groups mainly at the EU level or globally.